

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

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ABSTRACT:

The **final version** of the deliverable **D5.1 CLARIN/OPERAS/DARIAH/E-RIHS and the H2IOSC MarketPlace** examines in depth **the structure and functioning of the interconnection and mutual exchange system** between the four Research Infrastructures, with their associated services, and the H2IOSC MarketPlace.

To this end, it highlights the **pivotal role of a chosen set of integrated technologies** – ranging from OAI-PMH to APIs and the orchestration system – in setting up and ensuring communication and essential relationships between the different project components.

The deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the **H2IOSC MarketPlace**, which is coordinated by OPERAS-IT and acts as a **connection point** and single, dynamic and functional access environment for the collaborative sharing, use, and management of data and services.

It offers a detailed analysis of the nature and functions of **APIs and the orchestration system** – the technological core of the H2IOSC MarketPlace – which ensures the harmonised coordination and management of multiple systems, processes, applications and services, guaranteeing their efficient and effective mutual communication and integration, as well as optimal API performance. The **integration model** allows services to be managed and orchestrated without executing application workflows that directly impact the computational resources allocated by federated platforms to the MarketPlace itself.

This approach, which represents **the main element of innovation** compared to the marketplace models developed so far in federated platforms and *Open Science Clouds*, guarantees the possibility of integrating heterogeneous infrastructures into a distributed and flexible system. It optimises coordination between services without imposing operational constraints on how they are executed and also respects the possibility of integrating services at various levels of the federation and the platform.

In detail, the deliverable thoroughly reviews the nature and functioning of **APIs** and their main components. On the one hand, these are key elements to ensuring **effective relationships and communication** between the WPs and the integration of manifests in the data model and orchestration flows – a decisive step for providing some fundamental H2IOSC services. On the other hand, it is important to remark that they can be used in the same way and to the same purposes in other Open Science Cloud and Marketplace systems. In projects whose rules allow it, they can contribute to the project's economic sustainability by providing a scalable monetisation model: however, this does not apply to the H2IOSC model and will only be outlined in theory. Furthermore, after outlining the fundamental distinction between orchestration and composition, the deliverable explains the **strategic and operational importance of the orchestration system** in relation to the MarketPlace - which is designed as a point of exposure and orchestration of services - and illustrates **its features and functioning**.

The final section proposes **short-to-medium term developments** to be realised thanks to the H2IOSC MarketPlace and its advanced orchestration services. These developments aim to achieve ever greater integration between components, tools, functions and services, while offering users increasingly tailored solutions.

In conclusion, the deliverable offers a concise contextualisation of APIs and the orchestration system within the broader context of **DH European research space**, emphasising their wide range

of applications and potential for creating **open ecosystems** in which researchers, developers, and the public can access and use tools and resources.

The deliverable is completed by a **series of Annexes** corresponding to objective, quantitative and measurable **indicators** relevant to the **monitoring** and **ex-post assessment of the expected results**. With regard to the H2IOSC ecosystem and its MarketPlace, the five Annexes outline essential components, aspects and features of the latter, as well as key work methods and procedures that ensure its successful implementation, operation, and service delivery.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

H2IOSC	Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud
RI	Research Infrastructure
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
API	Application Programming Interface
IT	Information Technology
DH	Digital Humanities
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
XML-TEI	eXtensible Markup Language – Text Encoding Initiative
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
IAC	Istituto per le Applicazioni del Calcolo “Mauro Picone” of the Italian National Research Council
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AWS	Amazon Web Services
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
DSE	Digital Scholarly Edition
EAI	Enterprise Application Integration
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
REST	Representational State Transfer
CPU	Central Processing Unit
NLP	Natural Language Processing

SSO	Single Sign-On
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
JS	JavaScript
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
IdP	Identity Provider
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
UI	User Interface
ESB	Enterprise Service Bus
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IMATI	Istituto di Matematica Applicata e Tecnologie Informatiche "E. Magenes" of the Italian National Research Council
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
ISPC	Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale of the Italian National Research Council
MOLAB	MOBILE LABORatory
ISTI	Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione "Alessandro Faedo" of the Italian National Research Council
INO	Istituto Nazionale di Ottica of the Italian National Research Council
OVI	Opera del Vocabolario Italiano of the Italian National Research Council
TLIO	Tesoro della Lingua Italiana delle Origini
BTV	Bibliografia dei Testi Volgari
GATTO	Gestione degli Archivi Testuali del Tesoro delle Origini
EVT	Edition Visualization Technology
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ILC	Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale "Antonio Zampolli" of the Italian National Research Council
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
LOD	Linked Open Data
LLOD	Linguistic Linked Open Data
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
NER	Named Entity Recognition

HTR	Handwritten Text Recognition
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
FCS	Federated Content Search
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WSN	Wireless Sensor Networks
DASI	Digital Archive for the Study of pre-Islamic Arabian Inscriptions
EDM	Electric Discharge Machining
SCITEC	Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie Chimiche “Giulio Natta” of the Italian National Research Council
GPL 3	GNU General Public License v3.0
LMF	Lexical Markup Framework
SCF	Sub-Categorization Frame
IAAS	Infrastructure as a Service
SAAS	Software as a Service
CAAS	Container as a Service
LLM	Large Language Model
UX	User Experience
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
NANOTEC	Institute of Nanotechnology of the Italian National Research Council
CRUD	Create, Read, Update and Delete
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
APA	American Psychological Association
MLA	Modern Language Association
IEEE	institute for Electrical and Electronics Engineers
AMA	American Medical Association
CTA	Call To Action
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
SCI	Social and Cultural Innovation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID

INTRODUCTION

The final version of the deliverable **D5.1 CLARIN/OPERAS/DARIAH/E-RIHS and the H2IOSC MarketPlace¹** provides an accurate outline of the implementation procedures to connect the four Research Infrastructures and their associated services to the H2IOSC MarketPlace. To this end, it examines the **structure and functioning of the interconnection and mutual exchange system** between the four RIS and the MarketPlace in depth.

The deliverable provides a comprehensive **overview and a detailed description of the MarketPlace** developed within the H2IOSC Project. First, it shows how the marketplace acts as a **connection point**, a single, dynamic and functional access environment for the collaborative sharing, use and management of data and services. The H2IOSC MarketPlace, coordinated by OPERAS-IT, aims to increase the visibility and exploitation of the data sources, services and resources provided by the RIS participating in the Project, as well as by the research community in general, hosted in the H2IOSC National Cloud.

The deliverable focuses on **APIs** (Application Programming Interfaces) **and the “orchestration of services”**, the elements that promote the effective integration of the digital resources offered by the platform. APIs and their orchestration, in particular **WSO2 API Manager**, are thereby a key component of digital transformation. Through orchestration, in general, companies and institutions can modernise and innovate their IT infrastructure, integrating legacy systems in a modern and scalable way. This allows them to launch new digital functionalities and applications by drastically reducing time and simplifying integration with existing systems.

The **integration model** described in this deliverable enables the management and orchestration of services without executing application workflows that directly impact the computational resources allocated by the federated platform to the MarketPlace itself. This approach, which represents **the main element of innovation** compared to the marketplace models developed so far in federated platforms and *Open Science Clouds*, guarantees the feasibility of integrating heterogeneous infrastructures (and of integrating, in the future, other partners beyond those currently federated in H2IOSC) into a distributed and flexible system. It optimises coordination between services without imposing operational constraints on how they are executed, while it also respects the possibility of integrating services at the different levels of the federation and the platform.

This delivery includes a section dedicated to possible **monetisation strategies related to the integration model**, which will be presented as a theoretical contribution made available for project design in other cases. Monetising APIs via **WSO2 API Manager** can be an effective strategy to support the **economic sustainability** of long-term projects that, differently from H2IOSC, include services with associated usage fees. The benefits also extend to a macroeconomic scale.

¹ The deliverable has been prepared based on the comprehensive technical documentation provided by the M.E.T.A. company.

The final section proposes **future developments** in the short to medium term, thanks to the H2IOSC MarketPlace and its advanced orchestration services. These developments are intended to achieve an ever **greater integration between components**, tools, functions, and services, while offering **increasingly tailored solutions** to users and providers.

To conclude, API orchestration is contextualised within the **European Digital Humanities (DH) research space**. In fact, sharing data and resources via APIs supports the creation of **open ecosystems**, where researchers, developers and the public can access tools and resources. Public APIs enable external developers and researchers to create custom applications, integrate data visualisation tools, and develop new analyses, thereby expanding the scope and impact of the available resources. API orchestrators facilitate permission and security management, establishing access rules that protect sensitive data and regulating public access to resources.

1. THE H2IOSC MARKETPLACE

A marketplace is a ‘place’ where goods and services are exchanged (Cristofaro et al. 2024). In the European research space, marketplaces have been identified as essential tools to support the transition from traditional research to cloud-based infrastructures through centralised access to catalogues of resources and services. In the context of SSH, these resources and services may include relatively large and complex volumes of structured and heterogeneous data, together with software tools for querying, analysing and subsequently using these data and information repositories. In this scenario, the **Open Cloud Computing paradigm** has emerged as the dominant tool for distributing network infrastructure and resources, overcoming the need for complex and costly on-premises hardware/software systems for data management, including collaborative ones.

The marketplace acts as a **connection point** between different cloud networks and other network infrastructures, creating a single, dynamic and functional access environment for the collaborative sharing, use and management of data and services (Fig. 1). In this sense, the H2IOSC MarketPlace,² coordinated by OPERAS-IT, aims to enhance the visibility and exploitation of the data sources, services and resources provided by the RIs involved in the Cluster and the research community in general, hosted in the H2IOSC National Cloud (Sichera et al. 2024).

In this scenario, the orchestration of services in the MarketPlace is central to promoting the **effective integration** of the digital resources offered by the platform. This model of integration allows for the management and orchestration of services without executing application workflows that directly impact the computational resources allocated to the MarketPlace by the federated platforms.

This approach is a key innovation compared to marketplace models developed so far in federated platforms and *Open Science Clouds*. It guarantees the possibility of integrating heterogeneous infrastructures (in the future, not only those currently federated in H2IOSC) into a distributed and flexible system, optimising coordination between services without imposing operational constraints on how they are executed, and respecting the possibility of integrating services at the different levels of the federation and the platform.

As well as offering visibility and interoperability to all services made available by the H2IOSC federation, the MarketPlace is also able to present and integrate resources and services offered by external providers.

²CamelCase will be used throughout the document to identify the H2IOSC MarketPlace.

Fig. 1 - H2IOSC Shared Goals

1.1 THE MARKETPLACE AND THE OAI-PMH

The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)³ is a protocol for the exchange of metadata between digital archives. Its purpose is to promote interoperability between repositories, making content searchable and aggregable. The following table (Tab. 1) summarises its main features and elements:

Architecture	<p>Data Provider (e.g., digital libraries) A “data provider” makes data available to third parties, either free of charge as "open data" or for a fee. This data can be accessed through datasets, application programming interfaces (APIs), or databases.</p> <p>Service Provider: Collects and uses metadata (e.g., academic search engines).</p>
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³ For a detailed and comprehensive analysis of the OAI PMH, its key uses both in general terms to ensure interoperability in scientific research and its strategic role, as well as its main features and characteristics within H2IOSC, refer to deliverable D5.1 *CLARIN/OPERAS/DARIAH/E-RIHS and the H2IOSC MarketPlace - Interim*, Chapters 1 (pp. 9 ff.) and 2 (pp. 13 ff.) respectively.

Metadata	uses XML formats, typically Dublin Core.
Main operations	Identify, ListMetadataFormats, ListIdentifiers, ListRecords, GetRecord.
Technology	works via HTTP (GET or POST) and returns data in XML format.
Incrementality	supports incremental collection via date parameters, avoiding duplication.
Modularity	allows metadata sets to be specified, facilitating thematic selection.
Metadata format	supports multiple formats, but requires mandatory support of Dublin Core

Tab. 1 - Main features and elements promoting interoperability

Service orchestration in the H2IOSC MarketPlace is designed to coordinate interaction between services exposed by different infrastructures within the federation or by infrastructures and providers outside the federation itself.

The RIs participating in the H2IOSC federation populate the H2IOSC MarketPlace mainly in two ways. On the one hand, services published on marketplaces or infrastructure-specific platforms are catalogued in the H2IOSC MarketPlace through harvesting mechanisms, ensuring unified access to digital resources. On the other hand, services that are available for direct integration are published through push actions, subject to authorisation and compliance with established federation policies. In addition to cataloguing resources and individual services, the MarketPlace supports the orchestration of complex application workflows composed of multiple services in sequence (or in parallel, where applicable). In such cases, the MarketPlace coordinates the launch of each service in the defined order, managing dependencies and data transfer between services. Orchestration ensures that each service in the workflow is executed at the appropriate time in the respective provider's environment, until the entire application flow is completed. In the architectural scheme of the H2IOSC platform, service orchestration can also take place within specific platforms of the participating infrastructures. For simplicity, in this document, the 'orchestration' of services that takes place at the MarketPlace level, involving different platforms and service providers, will be referred to as 'orchestration', while that within individual infrastructures will be referred to as 'composition'.

As mentioned, the H2IOSC MarketPlace is a catalogue of heterogeneous objects (resources, services, and workflows). Services and resources can be called up directly or organised into 'descriptive' workflows; services that expose APIs corresponding to the model defined for the platform can be organised into 'application' workflows.

Marketplace

Searching and Viewing Harvested Resources - Items

Starting from the Marketplace Homepage, it is possible to search and view the harvested resources in the marketplace through different user flows and related functionalities

Marketplace H2IOSC

Fig. 2 - MarketPlace Users interface v.1

The Marketplace does not operate as an execution environment, but rather as an orchestrator that routes requests to their respective execution locations. The model adopted provides for a clear separation between orchestration and runtime environments, based on the architectural principle that data processing and the execution of services that expose APIs take place in a distributed manner in the remote IT systems of the infrastructures or, in general, of the service providers. Access to the services exposed in the Marketplace is regulated in accordance with the authentication and authorization policies established in the H2IOSC cluster, maintaining an elevated level of security without compromising the user experience. The Marketplace thus operates as a connection point between research infrastructures, without interfering with the execution mechanisms adopted by individual services and/or individual infrastructures.

1.2 FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS

User: Any individual who uses the Marketplace to access the catalogue of services and resources. This may comprise scientific and research personnel, technical staff, and members of the wider scientific and civil community, including students, teachers, professionals, external partners, citizen scientists, policymakers, and the interested public in general. For the purposes of this document, users are primarily considered to be those who launch services by activating the application workflows defined in the Marketplace.

Activate a workflow: request the start of a workflow through the Marketplace. In the context of the H2IOSC Marketplace, the user 'activates' a workflow consisting of one or more Marketplace services,

which they request to be executed according to the operational sequence and data exchange provided by the workflow. The MarketPlace takes charge of the request and forwards the steps in succession to the specific execution environments, where the services will be performed.

Launch (start) a service: request the execution of a service; in particular, from the point of view of this document, send a request relating to a service included in an application workflow activated by the MarketPlace user. The execution request is addressed to the technological infrastructure managed by the provider that makes the service available. The computational process of the service takes place in the computer system managed by the provider, i.e., outside the MarketPlace. Consequently, the MarketPlace does not take charge of the computational aspect of the services, but allows them to be launched or started within a flow that it manages (*orchestrates*) for the user's use.

Providing a service: Making a service available on the MarketPlace, either by direct registration (push) or by harvesting. The service provider makes the relevant information available in the MarketPlace catalogue, which describes its functionality and requirements, so that users can find and launch it, where applicable, insert it into a workflow, or transfer it to the execution site. Provision implies that the service is properly configured and that this configuration is recorded in the catalogue.

In order for the service to become orchestrable through the platform, the service provider (infrastructure, entity, or research group that develops and manages it), in addition to describing it through metadata, hardware/software requirements, and input/output parameters, specifies the methods for automatic invocation (API endpoint, credentials, application container, etc.). The MarketPlace will be able to send execution requests to the provider's system in accordance with the specifications provided. The provider ensures the availability and proper functioning of the execution environment for the service offered and updates the service information in case of changes or new versions.

MarketPlace – WSO2 Suite (orchestrator): System that coordinates the execution of services without executing them directly. In the H2IOSC Cluster, the MarketPlace acts as an orchestrator for application workflows: it receives requests from the user space and forwards them to the appropriate providers, managing the flow between request and result.

Execution environment: The infrastructure where the service is executed. The MarketPlace interacts with these external environments to orchestrate executions but does not replace them (the MarketPlace is not an execution environment).

Harvesting: Mechanism for automatically collecting information and metadata from external sources to populate the MarketPlace catalogue.

Descriptive workflow: Aggregation of services that only present a list with a reminder and reference function to the catalogue.

Application workflow: Aggregation of services with an organisational guidance function in the performance of an overall search and processing activity consisting of concatenated operations and with reference to the respective execution environments and the actual methods of data exchange between services. It determines an orchestrated sequence of multiple services or activities that are performed according to a predefined logical flow to achieve an overall result.

Orchestration: Workflow management system in which the various services that make up the flow are invoked locally or remotely by a system that governs the process, delegating its execution to other

specific systems or processes. In this document, *orchestration* refers only to the case in which the MarketPlace, operating with the WSO2 suite, ensures the orderly execution of the sequence. It differs from *composition* and *choreography*.

Composition: A workflow management system in which all services necessary for the execution of the flow are internal to the WSO2 infrastructure. It differs from orchestration and choreography (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 - The workflow management

Service (Metaservice): An orchestrated application workflow corresponds to a sequence of services or metaservices (application functionalities) executed in succession. A workflow may appear in the MarketPlace as a single feature, which can be referred to as a 'metaservice'. For orchestration purposes, a service or metaservice is considered a modular application unit that is accessible from the MarketPlace and can be combined with other services.

Resources: Organised collections of digital objects made available in the MarketPlace directly or through dedicated platforms and services.

2. RELATIONSHIPS AND COMMUNICATION WITH THE OTHER WPs: THE APIs

The MarketPlace receives services from various endpoints, i.e. WPs 2, 6, 7, 8. (Fig. 4). The centrality of **joint co-design** characterised the activities of WP5 related to its development and implementation. Close collaboration has been maintained with WP7 and its *Community Pilots*, particularly given the importance of the **survey** in relation to the entire project system and the articulation of the WPs for needs analysis and requirements definition.

For example, the Pilot RATIO⁴ is hosted on CNR's servers, more specifically at the IAC (Istituto per le Applicazioni del Calcolo "Mauro Picone") and harvested by the H2IOSC MarketPlace. Furthermore, text files are imported and converted to TEI/XML encoding via a service available in the MarketPlace⁵.

Fig. 4 - Relationships to the H2IOSC WP structure, from the point of view of WP5

⁴ For a detailed description of this Pilot, refer to deliverable D7.5 *OPERAS Pilots*, particularly Chapter 1, which focuses on RATIO (pp. 9 ff.).

⁵ The recommendation system adopted by the MarketPlace is derived from that developed for the E-RIHS services catalogue. This significant component is a paradigmatic example of the *structural interconnection and relationships*, deep and natively designed, between the RIs and the different Project components, as well as between the services of each RI and the MarketPlace. As the pivotal core of this interconnection, the MarketPlace is the fulcrum of the H2IOSC ecosystem, an integrated, open system comprising infrastructures, research communities, resources, tools and services. See also Annex 5 *The final version of the recommendation system based on AI*.

2.1 APIS AND THEIR MANAGEMENT AND ORCHESTRATION SYSTEM: DESCRIPTION AND MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

From a technical perspective, the H2IOSC MarketPlace, in line with its counterparts in Europe, is designed to offer functionalities on different levels to meet the needs of both administrators and users⁶.

The lowest level (**Level 0**) offers the constituent services of the MarketPlace (not included in the catalogue), which include:

- user-oriented functionalities (navigation, personal and shareable lists of 'favourites'...);
- governance-oriented functionalities (administration, statistics...).

The next level (**Level 1**) comprises the services offered by the MarketPlace catalogue. Let us consider the following as Level 1 services:

- the search interface that guides users in finding items of interest to them;
- services displayed by the MarketPlace.

The H2IOSC catalogue contains not only the services developed or virtualised specifically for the Cluster, but is also populated by the automatic and manual import of external resources (data and services). In particular, it guarantees interoperability with the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace developed by the SSHOC project (<https://sshopencloud.eu/>) and with the future EOSC EU Node marketplace (<https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/>). Likewise, external catalogues are able to access the H2IOSC MarketPlace via standard protocols for harvesting and exposing dedicated APIs.

The upper level (**Level 2**) offers tools for aggregating Level 1 services – first, the pilot services developed within the framework of H2IOSC WP7 into complex services (*workflows*)⁷.

Level 2 features:

- aggregations presenting only a list with (a) reminder function and (b) catalogue reference (**descriptive workflows**, similar to those available in the SSH Open Marketplace);
- aggregations with (a) the function of organisational guidance in the performance of an overall search and processing activity made up of concatenated operations and (b) reference to the respective execution environments and the actual modes of data exchange between services (**application workflows**).

The services that can be aggregated in workflows must respond to well-defined interoperability characteristics, both technical and in terms of content: for instance, the different functionalities (acquisition, transcription, encoding, analysis, layout, FAIRification...) incorporated into a workflow can be used to support the transition from the study of a manuscript to the Digital Scholarly Edition (DSE).

Thus, APIs define the rules and formats by which one application (resource or Level 1 service) can interact with another, allowing them to integrate and exchange information effectively without the need to know internal details.

⁶ Refer to Annex 1 of the deliverable D5.1 CLARIN/OPERAS/DARIAH/ERIHS and the H2IOSC MarketPlace - Interim, the *Alpha version of the catalogue of services* (pp. 30 ff.)

⁷ see for example: Community pilots. Innovative cross-domain services and environments <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/the-project/>.

The orchestration of APIs for application workflows

The need for a detailed presentation of the orchestration system stems from the technical specifications of the H2IOSC MarketPlace, which include the ability to create 'Level 2' services as aggregations that are not purely descriptive. Within these aggregations the MarketPlace must therefore be able to orchestrate the remote execution of individual 'Level 1' services for the user from a dedicated space, without either the processing or the passing of data between one service and another committing the resources of the MarketPlace itself, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 - Creating an orchestration sequence - <https://mi.docs.wso2.com/en/latest/learn/integration-tutorials/exposing-several-services-as-a-single-service/>

The following sections illustrate the scenario for the implementation of this orchestration and set out the guidelines for the development of an API Management system according to the functional requirements that emerged during the MarketPlace design phase.

2.2 AREAS OF USE OF THE API ORCHESTRATOR

The advent of cloud computing, coupled with features such as the modularity and scalability of web apps, has led to the need to manage and coordinate various computer microservices (APIs). This activity is performed by a component known as 'API orchestrator'. APIs and their orchestrators are therefore essential for implementing an interconnected digital infrastructure.

In a corporate environment, for example, one of the most common applications of APIs is the integration of internal systems, known as 'Enterprise Application Integration' (EAI). Here, APIs act as a conduit between systems such as CRM, ERP and accounting software, enabling an exchange of data that maintains alignment and consistency of information between departments. This type of integration also allows business processes to be automated, eliminating manual data entry and enabling the automatic monitoring of orders, inventories and the status of requests (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 - AWS Cloud model for service integration - <https://aws.amazon.com/what-is/enterprise-application-integration/>

In the context of external interactions, APIs facilitate integration with partners and suppliers, supporting real-time information exchange with the world outside the corporate organisation. This connectivity enables partners and distributors to operate in synchrony with the corporate systems. Similarly, APIs allow connection to third-party services such as payment platforms, geolocation systems and social media (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 - Display of services in an API marketplace - <https://apim.docs.wso2.com/en/4.2.0/get-started/apim-architecture/>

In **microservice-based** architectures, API orchestration plays a decisive role, by coordinating complex sequences of calls between microservices, each of which performs specific tasks. Additionally, in a microservice context, APIs allow centralised management of dependencies and security policies, ensuring that each microservice adheres to access and authentication guidelines established at an enterprise level.

Monetisation is a significant aspect of API orchestration. An increasing number of companies are now adopting API Economy models to generate value from their APIs by offering paid services or

subscription models. Monetisation-enabled API platforms enable the creation of digital service ecosystems, where companies can provide premium or value-added APIs to third parties, thereby converting technical capabilities into revenue streams.

API orchestration requires security and compliance management. Centralised authentication and authorisation make it possible to control who accesses what data, protecting resources and information. Log and audit management via orchestrators allows companies to monitor API usage, detect anomalies and ensure compliance with regulations, such as GDPR in Europe and HIPAA in the United States.

APIs and their orchestration are therefore a pivotal component of digital transformation. Through orchestration, the IT infrastructure of companies and institutions can be innovated and modernised, with legacy systems being integrated in a modern and scalable way. This enables them to introduce new digital functionalities and applications much more quickly and easily, while also making integration with existing systems simpler and more streamlined.

2.3 ORCHESTRATING APIS IN H2IOSC: A PILOT OF PILOTS FOR ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY AND REDUCED RESOURCE CONSUMPTION

One of the most important aspects of using orchestrators can be summarised by the simple statement that **the execution of APIs does not physically take place on the infrastructure hosting the orchestrator**. The orchestrator merely acts as an intermediary, managing the flow of requests between the client (e.g. a H2IOSC MarketPlace user) and the systems that actually implement the API (in H2IOSC, the pilot services of the Project and those that will be added, as well as, more generally, any other serviced resources). This **distributed architecture** offers significant technical and economic advantages due to the separation of computational responsibilities between the orchestrator and the remote systems (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 - Architecture with and without orchestrator - <https://www.axopen.com/blog/2020/08/api-kong-gateway-presentation-demonstration/>

The orchestrator primarily operates as a control centre and is responsible for processing metadata, managing authorisations, monitoring requests, and applying rules such as limiting the number of requests within a given time interval (*throttling*), as well as temporarily saving responses to speed up subsequent requests (*caching*). These activities involve relatively little use of computing resources, since they do not include processing the API's fundamental logic. For instance, a REST (Representational State Transfer) request sent via an orchestrator could be authenticated, verified, and redirected to the remote server without any significant computation of the data being performed. This results in moderate CPU, memory and bandwidth consumption for the orchestrator, compared to the load borne by the remote systems implementing the API.

In terms of network resources, the orchestrator acts as a gateway. It receives requests from clients, possibly applies compression or transformation policies to messages, and forwards requests to remote servers. Therefore, bandwidth consumption depends on the volume and size of requests received. However, compared to a fully centralised infrastructure, an orchestrator allows optimisation of network transfers.

API orchestrators make it possible to handle scenarios in which **large amounts of data** must be processed **without the data passing through or being stored on the orchestrator's own machine**. This approach is possible thanks to the architecture based on remote endpoints. In practice, the orchestrator acts as a mediator that routes requests and responses between the client and the various endpoints, without interfering with the actual flow of data.

For example, if a user needs to send 2TB of data to a first endpoint for processing and then receive a similarly large, generated result from a second endpoint, the orchestrator allows a direct connection between the client and the endpoints. This means that **the data is neither temporarily stored nor processed by the orchestrator**, thus reducing the computational load and storage requirements on the machine running the orchestration software.

To implement the solution to such a scenario, an orchestrator uses streaming and routing protocols to allow data to flow directly between the parties involved, keeping the orchestrator as a simple controller of the process. This design is particularly useful for data-intensive applications such as batch processing or real-time data streams, where direct transmission improves performance and reduces the operational costs associated with the orchestrator's infrastructure. Resources such as CPU and network on the orchestrator are mainly used to authenticate, authorise and track transactions, while the bulk of the computational load is handled by the endpoints themselves. This approach not only reduces bottlenecks on the orchestrator's machine but also ensures better overall scalability of the system. It is particularly suitable in distributed or cloud-native contexts, where the separation of tasks between orchestrator and endpoint can greatly improve efficiency.

Instead, the remote system implementing the API (i.e. the service called by the MarketPlace application workflow) is responsible for the actual execution of application logic, such as database queries, algorithmic processing or access to external resources. This means that the main computational load, including the handling of complex mathematical calculations or the processing of large datasets, is completely left to the remote system. This separation of roles makes it possible to scale the infrastructure more efficiently, as on the one hand the orchestrator only requires sufficient resources to handle the increasing number of requests, while on the other hand the sizing of the remote systems depends on the complexity of the operations performed.

From a technical point of view, this distributed approach also allows the use of advanced monitoring capabilities. Orchestrators can record detailed metrics, such as API response time, the number of

requests per second or any backend errors, providing tools for optimisation and debugging, as well as information on user habits that is useful for eventual *landscaping*.

A concrete example may concern an application that uses APIs for linguistic analysis on historical texts. The orchestrator could receive requests from clients, check authentication and user quotas, and then forward the data to the remote system running NLP algorithms on powerful infrastructure. The orchestrator consumes few resources for network management and policy verification, while the backend must scale computational resources to process large datasets. This division offers tangible benefits, including reduced computational cost on the central infrastructure and greater flexibility in resource allocation.

2.4 H2IOSC: SCENARIO FOR PERFORMING APIS THROUGH ORCHESTRATION

1. The user accesses mp.h2iosc.cnr.it via SSO authentication managed by Keycloak with the username mionome@dominiobase.fyi.
2. On the `execute.html` page, the user can upload a text file (e.g. a chapter of the *Aristotelian telescope*).
3. The user has two REST endpoints with authentication:
 - **First endpoint:** Receives a file as a parameter and returns a file with the first 10 words of the text. Authorised access with mionome@dominio1.fyi.
 - **Second endpoint:** Receives a file as a parameter and returns a file with the initial letters of the words within the input file. Authorised access with mionome@dominio2.fyi.
4. Expected workflow:
 - The user starts uploading the file to `run.html`.
 - The file is sent in pass-through mode to the first endpoint.
 - In asynchronous mode, the output of the first endpoint is automatically sent to the second.
 - The user finds the output file generated by the second endpoint when he returns to the `execute.html` page.

Analytical description

At mp.h2iosc.cnr.it, the user authenticates to access its backend via a SSO managed by Keycloak with the username (as an example) mionome@dominiobase.fyi.

Within the `execute.html` page, it is possible to upload a text file, e.g. a chapter of the *Aristotelian telescope*.

The user has access to two endpoints that expose REST APIs that require authentication to be executed.

The first endpoint exposes an API that receives a file as a parameter and returns a text with the first 10 words of the file sent. On this first endpoint, the user is authorised to log in via the username mionome@dominio1.fyi.

The second endpoint exposes an API that receives a text as a parameter and returns as output a file with a string inside formed by the initial letters of the words of the input text. On this second endpoint, the user is authorised to log in through the username mionome@dominio2.fyi.

Given these premises:

- pressing a button within execute.html starts an operation that sends the loaded file to the first endpoint;
- meanwhile, the user exits the page;
- when the first endpoint returns its output, this output is automatically sent to the second endpoint;
- when the user returns to their back end, they will find how to download the output generated by the second endpoint.

Requested solution

The described scenario can be implemented using a combination of various tools and packages such as Kong API Gateway, Keycloak, Apache Kafka, RabbitMQ, Apache Camel, Tyk Gateway, WSO2 API Manager, WSO2 Identity Server (this is just a selection of free or open-source software). For convenience, the solution described below uses WSO2 API Manager, Keycloak and WSO2 Identity Server, but it can also be implemented using different combinations.

The solution mainly involves an implementation of the WSO2 platform, using the **WSO2 API Manager** (WSO2 APIM) and the **WSO2 Identity Server** (WSO2 IS) for authentication management and Single Sign-On (SSO) integration. The described features may vary depending on the versions of the various components used.

Authentication and SSO via Keycloak

- WSO2 Identity Server can be configured to integrate with Keycloak as an external Identity Provider. In this case, the user authenticates at mp.h2iosc.cnr.it via Keycloak, and WSO2 IS recognises the credentials issued by Keycloak thanks to an **identity federation**.
- When a user logs in with mionome@dominiobase.fyi at mp.h2iosc.cnr.it, WSO2 IS can manage the user's session and provide a valid OAuth2 token that can be used to authorise calls to the REST API at the various endpoints.

WSO2 API Manager for managing APIs and multiple credentials

WSO2 API Manager (APIM) offers support for orchestrating REST API calls, managing authentications, and supporting asynchronous flows.

Step 1: Configure API proxies for the two endpoints

- **Creating the first proxy API:** Create a proxy API on WSO2 APIM representing the first endpoint (the one that returns the first 10 words of the file).
 - Configure the authentication credentials for this endpoint using **OAuth2** or **Basic Auth** with the user mionome@dominio1.fyi.
 - Authentication credentials for dominio1.fyi can be stored and managed via WSO2 APIM's **Secret Management**, ensuring security.
- **Creating the second proxy API:** Create a proxy API for the second endpoint, the one that returns the initial letter string.
 - Configure authentication for this second endpoint using the username mionome@dominio2.fyi.
 - Also, for dominio2.fyi, use the WSO2 APIM secret management system to store credentials securely.

Step 2: Creating a sequence of mediators to orchestrate processes

- **Mediation Flows:** Use the WSO2 APIM mediation framework to orchestrate the asynchronous flow. This can be done by configuring an integration between the two endpoints with the following steps:
 - **Asynchronous sending of the file to the first endpoint:** When the user uploads a file to run.html and presses the button, send the file to the WSO2 Proxy API for the first endpoint.
 - **Storage of the response:** Once the response has been received from the first endpoint (with the first 10 words), use an internal **messaging store**, such as a database, to store the response.
 - **Sending to the second endpoint:** Configure an automated process (e.g. using a cron job or a trigger configured within the APIM itself) that retrieves the output of the first endpoint and sends it to the second endpoint.

Step 3: Publishing the output and asynchronous notifications

WSO2 supports an asynchronous flow to notify results, which is useful when the user exits the page:

- **Callback or polling:** To allow the user to retrieve the resulting data, one of the following options can be implemented:
 - **Notification via callback:** Implement a webhook or dedicated endpoint at mp.h2iosc.cnr.it that receives a notification as soon as the second endpoint has generated the final output. In this case, the user can be notified about the availability of the file.
 - **Polling the output:** Alternatively, the WSO2 APIM portal or a JS function in the run.html page can poll periodically to check the availability of the file at mp.h2iosc.cnr.it.
- **Downloading the file:** Once the second endpoint has generated the final file, you can make it available for download, for example, by creating a temporary access URL (via WSO2 APIM) or by providing a direct link in the run.html page.

2.5 ORCHESTRATION COMPONENTS AND ASYNCHRONOUS SUPPORT

What are Mediators? In WSO2 API Manager, *mediators* are components that allow transformations and intermediate logic to be performed during the transit of API requests through the system. With mediators, it is possible to transform, filter, route or enrich requests and responses without changing the underlying API.

How do they work? Mediators work within a *mediation sequence*. When an API is called, traffic is routed through the mediator sequence, which may include:

- **Payload Factory Mediator:** to modify the content of the request or response.
- **Call Mediator:** to make calls to other services (such as the second endpoint, in this case).
- **Store Mediator:** to store the request or response in a messaging store (see below).
- **Enrich Mediator:** to add or modify data in the message.

In practice, using a sequence of mediators, it is possible to orchestrate the flow that sends the file to the first endpoint, then automatically sends the result to the second endpoint, and finally notifies the user or updates a status for downloading (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9 - Transports and mediators - <https://mi.docs.wso2.com/en/latest/get-started/key-concepts/>

What is the Messaging Store? The *messaging store* is a feature of the WSO2 API Manager that allows messages (such as requests or API responses) to be stored in a temporary storage area, which is useful for asynchronous applications, where responses are not immediate and must be processed later.

How does it work? The messaging store is entirely managed by WSO2 and does not require API endpoints to be modified. It functions as an internal 'store and forward' system to facilitate asynchronous operations.

Store Mediator: allows messages to be placed in a messaging store. For instance, a reply obtained from the first endpoint can be stored in the messaging store.

Message Processor: A message processor retrieves messages from the store and sends them to another endpoint or performs other actions. The message processor can be configured to operate in asynchronous mode, automatically calling the second endpoint as soon as the response is available.

What is a Callback? A *callback* is a mechanism for notifying an external system that an operation has been completed and that the results are available. In a WSO2 context, a callback can be configured in various ways.

If the target system supports webhooks or notification endpoints, WSO2 can send a notification when the flow is complete.

Alternatively, you can configure an internal notification or status update that makes the results available to the user when they return to the page.

How does it work? When the second endpoint has finished processing, a mediator sequence can send a notification (or callback) informing mp.h2iosc.cnr.it of the availability of the output file. If

mp.h2iosc.cnr.it has an endpoint that supports webhooks, WSO2 can automatically send the notification to the site, which can update the user interface with a link to the final file.

What is Polling? *Polling* is a technique in which a system periodically checks the availability of an output. In this case, mp.h2iosc.cnr.it can periodically send requests to WSO2 to check whether the second endpoint has produced the output.

How does it work? Polling is an operation entirely managed by WSO2 and **does not require any changes to the endpoints**. It allows the status of the user request to be updated with repeated calls until the file is ready.

Configure a *polling API* in WSO2 that mp.h2iosc.cnr.it can call to check the status of processing.

This API can return status information, such as 'Waiting for completion' or 'File available'.

Once the second endpoint has produced the output file, WSO2 updates the status to 'completed', and mp.h2iosc.cnr.it receives a positive response with the link to the file for download.

2.6 ARCHITECTURE, INSTALLATION, AND DEVELOPMENT ENVIRONMENT

WSO2 offers various ways to install and configure its main components.

Docker and Docker Compose: WSO2 provides official Docker images for WSO2 API Manager and WSO2 Identity Server, which can be used to quickly configure the container environment. Docker Compose can be used to start both components with the necessary configuration.

WSO2 API Manager and WSO2 Identity Server are two separate Docker containers, each with its own official Docker image. Here is how they work together and why they are distributed separately.

WSO2 API Manager

- It is the main component for managing and displaying the API.
- It offers features such as proxy API creation, throttling, security (including authentication and authorisation), monitoring and integration flow management (mediation).
- It supports OAuth2 configuration for the API, so it can act as an **OAuth2 client** by requesting access tokens from an authorisation server such as WSO2 Identity Server.

WSO2 Identity Server

- It is the component responsible for identity management and authentication.
- It is used as an **Identity Provider (IdP)**, handling Single Sign-On (SSO) authentication via OAuth2/OpenID Connect, SAML, etc.
- It can be configured to manage OAuth2 tokens, which the API Manager uses to authenticate users or to manage authentication delegation to endpoints.
- It allows managing multiple users for different domains, also supporting federated authentication.

Integration and Communication between Containers

In a typical containerised configuration:

- **WSO2 API Manager** is configured to use **WSO2 Identity Server** as an external Identity Provider.
- The two containers communicate via a common Docker network.
- For instance, when a protected API is called via the API Manager, it interfaces with the Identity Server to verify credentials and obtain access tokens.

Configuration on Docker

To configure the two containers in Docker:

1. **WSO2 API Manager** and **WSO2 Identity Server** must be started with their respective configuration files, configuring the API Manager to refer to the Identity Server as Identity Provider.
2. It is common to use **Docker Compose** to orchestrate containers, defining both services with their network configurations, ports, environment variables and volumes.

Below is a possible example of minimal configuration in Docker Compose:

```
version: '3.7'
services:
  wso2apim:
    image: wso2/wso2am:latest
    ports:
      - "8280:8280" # HTTP API
      - "8243:8243" # HTTPS API
    networks:
      - wso2_network
    environment:
      - IS_HOST=wso2is # Service name of container Identity Server
      - CONFIG_FILES=/path/apim/configs

  wso2is:
    image: wso2/wso2is:latest
    ports:
      - "9443:9443" # HTTPS IS
    networks:
      - wso2_network
    environment:
      - CONFIG_FILES=/path/is/configs

networks:
  wso2_network:
    driver: bridge
```

Architecture Configuration

This architecture primarily requires the configuration of WSO2 API Manager and, optionally, WSO2 Identity Server for managing SSO and multiple credentials. Most configurations and functionalities, such as Single Sign-On and OAuth2 integrations, can be realised via the WSO2 web interface

(Management Console). However, some more advanced elements require the definition of custom logic via XML files or configuration languages.

a. Configuration of API Manager

The configuration of the WSO2 API Manager requires the creation of the following components:

- **API Proxy:** For each endpoint (first and second), an API Proxy must be configured via the WSO2 API Manager Management Console, where the API path, authorisations, security policies, etc. are defined.
- **Mediation Sequence:** The orchestration between the first and second endpoint requires a sequence of mediators, which can be configured via:
 - **UI of WSO2:** The Management Console offers basic tools for creating simple mediators (such as logging, routing and payloads).
 - **XML scripting:** For more advanced mediators (such as Message Store and Call Mediator), it is necessary to define routing and transformation logic via XML files in WSO2's ESB (Enterprise Service Bus) configuration language. More complex mediators require WSO2-specific XML scripting.

b. Credentials Management

In order to store multiple credentials and access the two endpoints with different users, WSO2 offers tools to securely configure permissions and access to OAuth2 tokens, or static credentials:

- **Secret Management:** The credentials for the two domains (domain1.fyi and domain2.fyi) can be stored in a WSO2 vault, integrated with API Manager, for later retrieval and use by brokers. This configuration can be done in the WSO2 UI.

c. Asynchronous Notification Options

The implementation of asynchronous notifications requires intermediate configuration or customisation:

- **Messaging Store and Message Processor:** These components can be configured via the WSO2 UI to define asynchronous polling or automatic triggering to send the result of the first endpoint to the second.
- **Callback or Polling:** WSO2 does not provide a direct polling or callback function for the front-end, but a status endpoint can be implemented as a custom API in API Manager. Polling logic must be developed client-side (mp.h2iosc.cnr.it) to periodically check the status of the operation.

3. MANIFESTS, DATA MODEL, AND APIs - TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF ON-DEMAND EXECUTION: H2IOSC WP6 MANIFEST INTEGRATION

WP6 of H2IOSC is dedicated to the activities related to the servification, virtualisation and remotisation of existing tools and services available at the RIs involved (CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS), based on the results of the mapping tasks carried out in WP2, standardisation (WP3), interoperability (WP4) and realisation of the MarketPlace (WP5) (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10 - H2IOSC WPs structure - <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/the-project/>

Among the activities carried out by WP6, great emphasis was placed on the creation of a manifest for the exposure of services (see Deliverable D6.1, section “Servification, Virtualization and Remotization plan”). To integrate such a manifest (containing OpenAPI Definitions) into WSO2 API Manager, it is plausible to adopt a flow that exploits the API management and orchestration capabilities of WSO2. The process for importing JSON/YAML manifest containing OpenAPI Definition (see Deliverable D6.2 describing OpenAPI adoption for H2IOSC services) URLs is described below, based on the manifests available during the project at h2manifests.us.to. The manifests will eventually be made available either separately by the four RIs (with each RI exposing their own manifest) or centrally within a dedicated H2IOSC subdomain. A JSON schema (developed in WP6 jointly with WP5) is also available on GitHub (<https://github.com/phoenixbf/h2m>).

3.1 INTEGRATION OF WP6 MANIFESTS INTO THE DATA MODEL AND ORCHESTRATION FLOWS

An essential element of the H2IOSC platform architecture is the integration of the manifests generated by the services and defined in WP6, which constitute the formal description of the services to be made

available in the MarketPlace. Produced in a standardised, machine-readable format, these manifests include various metadata for each service, including the identifier, input/output parameters, endpoints, OpenAPI definitions, and the level of technological, social, legal, and organisational maturity. The manifest thus acts as a descriptive interface between the service provider and the MarketPlace, providing a bridge between the local development environment and the orchestration system. The exposure of the manifest allows for the immediate and automated registration and publication of the service within the MarketPlace and defines its compatibility with the platform's data model, ensuring that each described element can be understood and managed by the orchestration system.

In this context, the MarketPlace uses the data in the manifests and the specifications provided therein to

- verify the semantic and functional compatibility of the services to be registered with respect to the Federated Data Model of the H2IOSC project (developed in WP4);
- automatically populate the service catalogue and the metadata required for orchestrated invocation;
- configure the operating parameters in the application workflows, ensuring the correct interaction between different services and compliance with execution, timing, security, and availability constraints.

The systematic adoption of these manifests, in accordance with the specifications defined in WP6, essentially simplifies the onboarding of new services, improves the automation of orchestration operations, and promotes system scalability. In this model, the MarketPlace does not require any manual writing and/or rewriting of metadata or service definitions, as it automatically maps the content of the manifests to the entities of its data model. The integration of these manifests therefore allows for standardisation of the way services are exposed and consumed, simplifying the orchestration process and improving the ability to aggregate services into application workflows. This approach ensures greater interoperability between different infrastructures and enables the implementation of a modular and extensible orchestration model.

3.2 LOADING MANIFESTS IN THE WSO2 API MANAGER

Each manifest available via the given URL contains a range of information, including a URL that exposes an OpenAPI definition (in JSON or YAML format) describing the REST API specifications of the service. Specific configurations of **Rate Limiting**, **Throttling** and **Access Policies** may also be included in the manifest, to define API access modes and limits directly at the import stage.

The following actions will be required to integrate these manifests into the WSO2 API Manager:

- Downloading the Manifest:** Make an HTTP request to download the JSON/YAML manifest directly from the specific URL;
- Extract the OpenAPI Definition URL:** From the retrieved manifest, locate the field containing the OpenAPI definition URL of the specific REST service. In a JSON-like manifest, the part relating to the exposed service might look like this:

```
{
  "service": {
    "name": "Example Service",
    "openapi_url": http://anyurl.org/openapi/v1/example-service.yaml
    "policies": {
      "rate_limit": "500rpm",
      "throttling": "burst=5",
      "access_level": "OAuth2".
    }
  }
}
```

- c. **Importing the OpenAPI Definition into the WSO2 API Manager:** Use the URL of the OpenAPI definition to import the API into WSO2 via the **Management Console**.

Configuring Periodic Manifest Synchronisation

Since OpenAPI endpoint specifications may be updated or undergo changes, it is essential to keep API configurations synchronised with new versions or changes in status. In addition to technical updates, the manifest may indicate the **operational status** of the service, which may include:

- **CREATED:** The API has been created and is in an initial configuration phase. It is not yet available to end users.
- **PRE-RELEASED:** The API is ready for testing but has not yet been published for general use.
- **PUBLISHED:** The API is available for use by users. In this state, it is fully supported and accessible.
- **BLOCKED:** Access to the API is temporarily blocked for maintenance, security, or policy reasons. It is not available for use until further notice.
- **DEPRECATED:** The API is still available, but its use is discouraged because it has been replaced or is due to be withdrawn. Migrating to a more up-to-date alternative is recommended.
- **RETIRED:** The API has been discontinued and is no longer accessible to users.

To automate the synchronisation process and keep WSO2 up to date with respect to these states, a script can be created that periodically executes a call to the manifest endpoint for each service (e.g., using cron jobs on Linux). The script can check for changes in service specifications and states, ensuring that the WSO2 API Manager automatically updates or notifies these changes.

3.3 INTEGRATION OF A REMOTISATION SERVICE

Within the H2IOSC WP6, OPERAS is entrusted with the realisation of an offline resource utilisation system (task 6.10, “remotisation”). A remote application allows users to prepare data offline and then send it to a remote endpoint once a suitable network connection is available. By integrating an API orchestrator in this scenario, the transfer of data to the remote endpoint is done efficiently and securely, with the **orchestrator’s role limited to coordinating communication** between the client (the user sending the data) and the endpoint, **without the need to directly store or manage the data itself on the system hosting the orchestrator**.

The orchestrator acts as a gateway for the transfer, brokering requests and ensuring authentication, access control and validation of requests, but without introducing an intermediate step involving the data itself. Consequently, the data prepared by the user is sent directly from the application to the remote endpoint, with the **orchestrator supervising the process at the logical and protocol levels**. The same principle also applies to the response data generated by the remote endpoint, which can be downloaded by the user directly without passing through the orchestrator's system.

This mode of operation is technically advantageous in scenarios requiring the transfer of large volumes of data, as it avoids network and computing overload on the orchestrator's system. The orchestrator's infrastructure is only used to handle light network requests, such as connection management, configuration of access policies, and logging of operations, while the actual data transfer takes place directly between the client and the endpoint.

This **'pass-through' architecture** optimises transfer efficiency, reduces the computational load on the orchestrator and ensures that the data stays as close as possible to the systems processing it. The desired result is a lean ecosystem that maintains scalability and security without introducing network or computational bottlenecks. Using the WSO2 environment may require the use of additional tools, such as the WSO2 Micro Integrator.

Architecture's Advantages

- **Centralised security:** With the WSO2 Identity Server, Keycloak can be integrated for SSO and securely manage domain1.fyi and domain2.fyi credentials without them being visible or accessible to the end user.
- **Automation:** WSO2 APIM supports asynchronous mediation flows and configurations, allowing the sequence of calls to the two endpoints to be automated.
- **User status management:** Even if the user exits the page, WSO2 APIM manages the asynchronous flow, enabling the operation to be completed and the results to be made available as soon as they are ready.

3.4 DEFINITION OF A SCALABLE MONETISATION MODEL

Additionally, a scalable APIs-based monetisation model via the **WSO2 API Manager** is here presented as a possible strategy for supporting the **economic sustainability** of similar long-term projects that include services with associated usage *fees*. While H2IOSC does not support such a model, nor is expected to do it in the future, WSO2, as described beforehand, provides the necessary tools to monetise and optimise backend resources by integrating API control, access, and billing functionalities (Pellino et al. 2022). The benefits also extend to a macroeconomic scale. The WSO2 API Manager allows customised API pricing plans to be configured to monetise different service levels according to pricing models such as:

- **Consumer models:** charging per number of requests (e.g. € 0.01 per request) or amount of data transferred. This model is flexible to adapt to users' usage load and balances costs with generated value.
- **Subscription-based models:** monthly or annual subscription levels with specific usage thresholds (such as a limit on monthly requests), ensuring a constant income forecast.

- **Freemium models:** free access to basic functionality with additional costs for premium functionality. This model can attract new users and encourage a gradual conversion to paid plans. With a tiered approach and the possibility to change plans according to user landscape modifications, a contribution to long-term sustainability can be provided.

Configuration of Throttling and Quotas Management

To ensure that resources are used efficiently, it is crucial to implement tailor-made **throttling and quota policies**. WSO2 enables:

- Limit requests per user or app according to the plan subscribed to.
- Set throttling thresholds to prevent API abuse, while ensuring that premium users receive priority.

This resource management optimises performance and reduces operating costs, increasing the profitability and economic lifetime of the platform.

API Monitoring and Data Analysis to Optimise Monetisation

With WSO2's **integrated monitoring**, it is possible to track API performance and user behaviour. The obtained data allows you to:

- Identify the most used APIs and the functionalities that generate the most value, facilitating rate optimisation.
- Analyse usage data and user habits to adapt tariff plans and promotions.
- Monitor user satisfaction to improve the service, foster loyalty and reduce the drop-out rate.

These reports enable turnover forecasting, allowing more precise planning of costs and investments over time.

Invoicing and Integration with Payment Systems

WSO2 supports integrations with **external payment systems**, enabling the automation of revenue management. Through integration with payment gateways, it is possible:

- Automate monthly or annual invoicing.
- Enable notifications and subscription updates to promote plan upgrades.
- Efficiently manage renewals, deferred invoicing and due dates, ensuring a stable income stream.

Incentives and Partnerships to Increase API Adoption

A long-term monetisation strategy may include incentives to expand the user base and partnerships with companies that could benefit from the APIs. Possible approaches include:

- Discounted and promotional offers for strategic partners to encourage the integration of the APIs into their systems.
- Referral programmes to incentivise current users to promote the APIs.
- Creation of customised business plans with multi-user licences, guaranteeing stable revenues and fostering market penetration.

4. ORCHESTRATION AND COMPOSITION. ROLE OF THE MARKETPLACE IN THE ORCHESTRATION SYSTEM

‘Orchestration’ refers to any workflow management system in which the various services that make up the flow are invoked, either locally or remotely, by a system that governs the process, delegating its execution to other specific systems or processes. As previously explained, orchestration only refers to the case in which the Marketplace, operating with the WSO2 suite, ensures the orderly execution of the sequence. In this scenario, the various services that make up a workflow are invoked remotely, on machines external to the system that governs the process, while the WSO2 suite acts as a central coordinator, sending requests to external services, managing responses, and composing the results.

This implies:

- The use of network protocols to interact with distributed services.
- The need for polling, callback, or asynchronous event management mechanisms to check the execution status.
- Greater complexity in managing network errors, timeouts, and fault tolerance.

We refer to this in this document as ‘composition’ in cases where service orchestration takes place within a particular marketplace or platform of an infrastructure or service provider, and where all services necessary for workflow execution are therefore internal to the WSO2 infrastructure. In this case:

- The workflow is executed entirely within the WSO2 execution environment, leveraging the hardware resources of the single infrastructure or service provider (on-premises or in a private cloud).
- There is no need to configure polling or callbacks, as the services are already directly and synchronously accessible.
- Execution is more efficient, reliable, and easily monitored, thanks to the coexistence of components in the same environment.

The orchestration model adopted in H2IOSC has been designed to support flexible and extensible management, allowing the integration of additional research infrastructures and service providers in addition to the currently federated infrastructures. This ensures that the system can evolve over time, maintaining an orchestration framework that can adapt to the future needs of the Project.

Aspect	Orchestration	Composition
Execution	Remote (on external systems)	Local (inside WSO2)
Service Management	Network Invocations	Direct access to services
Complexity	High: Requires callback/polling handling	Low: Synchronous execution
Performance	They depend on the network	Optimised by the internal environment
Monitoring	Decoupled	Centralised

Tab. 2 - Orchestration framework

4.1 DISTINCTION BETWEEN MARKETPLACE AND EXECUTION ENVIRONMENTS

A fundamental element of the H2IOSC architecture is the clear separation between the MarketPlace, designed as a point of exposure and orchestration of services, and the runtime environments, responsible for the actual execution of the APIs and services included in the application workflows. The MarketPlace does not execute services directly; rather, it acts as a mediator between user requests and the infrastructures that host and execute the APIs. To ensure effective integration between orchestration and runtime environments, the H2IOSC system is based on a distributed architecture, in which each infrastructure manages the execution of its own services in accordance with its own access and security policies.

4.2 LAYERED ORCHESTRATION MODEL

The orchestration architecture in the H2IOSC MarketPlace is based on a layered model, which allows the different phases of the API management process and application workflows to be separated. This model is divided into the following operational layers:

- *Access and authentication layer*: interaction between users and the MarketPlace takes place through an authentication system that regulates access to the catalogue of exposed services.
- *API management level*: the MarketPlace offers a unified interface for accessing services, regulating security policies and defining how APIs are exposed in the MarketPlace. This level manages user requests and routes them to the appropriate services.
- *Orchestration and integration level*: the MarketPlace coordinates interaction between APIs, enabling the creation of complex application workflows. This layer manages request routing, data transformation between different services, and execution flow control.
- *Remote runtime execution layer*: APIs are actually executed in the runtimes of federated infrastructures, which can expose services through proprietary API managers or as individual instances. This layer is responsible for computing and processing the data requested by users.

4.3 DESCRIPTIVE AND APPLICATION WORKFLOWS IN THE H2IOSC MARKETPLACE

The H2IOSC MarketPlace manages two types of workflows: descriptive workflows and application workflows (workflows are aggregations of services).

1. *Descriptive workflows* only present a list with a reminder function and reference to the catalogue, similar to those available in the SSH Open Marketplace. They represent the possibility that certain services are linked together, without defining an execution. Therefore, these workflows describe a model of potential interoperability between services exposed in the Marketplace, but no execution instance can be activated from them.
2. *Application workflows*, on the other hand, are the main innovation brought by H2IOSC to its marketplace model. These are aggregations of services with an organisational guidance function in the performance of overall research and processing activities consisting of concatenated operations. They provide for the included services to refer to their respective execution environments and the actual methods of data exchange between them. Unlike descriptive workflows, therefore, they are true orchestrations of services, i.e. operational compositions that can be modelled and executed by users.

Once created and published, application workflows can be viewed as individual services in the user space or within the Marketplace. This means that users can call up a workflow as if it were a service itself (also considered a meta-service in this case), enabling it to be executed in accordance with the access policies defined in the system.

Importing and using services and application workflows

When a user wants to use a service (whether it is a single API or an application workflow), they import it into their user space to execute it. This process ensures that the user has control over executions and can configure any parameters before calling the service.

The H2IOSC Marketplace ensures that requests are forwarded to the appropriate runtime environments, respecting any restrictions defined in the access and usage policies.

Operational sequence for executing a workflow

1. The authenticated user creates a workflow in their user space or selects one from those already published on the Marketplace and starts its execution through the web interface, specifying the configuration parameters.
2. The Marketplace (orchestrator) receives the request from the user. Step by step, the Marketplace forwards an execution request to the actual service provider, using APIs or other agreed communication systems. The Marketplace includes all the necessary parameters and metadata for the provider to actually start the service on their platform in the request.
3. The provider launches and executes the service in their environment (server, cluster, cloud, etc.). The Marketplace waits for the outcome, periodically checking the provider's system for progress, if applicable.
4. Once execution is complete, the provider makes the results (output) of the service available to the Marketplace, along with any status information (success, error, log, etc.).

5. The output is used as input for the next service defined in the application workflow sequence, thus returning to step 3 for each of the services that make up the workflow.
6. At the end of the execution of the last service defined in the workflow, the user receives a notification via their interface. Any output is stored in the web space defined by the user in the orchestration project and in any case outside the user space in the MarketPlace.

4.4 ARCHITECTURE OF THE H2IOSC MARKETPLACE

The MarketPlace architecture is based on an API management and distributed orchestration system that uses various applications from the WSO2 family (WSO2 API Manager, WSO2 Micro Integrator, and WSO2 Identity Server). This provides a centralised framework for managing API access (which also regulates security and monetisation policies) and a platform for implementing advanced integration processes, coordinating communication between services, and managing asynchronous data flows. The architecture is supported by an authentication system that ensures controlled access to resources through federated and standardised mechanisms.

The architecture responds to the following operational levels:

- Access and authentication level: Keycloak manages user authentication to the MarketPlace.
- API management level: WSO2 API Manager provides the interface for accessing services and enforces execution policies.
- Orchestration and integration level: WSO2 Micro Integrator coordinates the interaction between APIs by executing orchestration projects:
 - developed locally by the user through a component for Visual Studio Code and then uploaded to the platform;
 - created online on the MarketPlace through a wizard;
 - created online on Jupiter notebooks integrated into the platform.
- Remote runtime execution level: API execution always takes place in the runtimes of federated infrastructures.

4.5 API EXECUTION MODEL IN THE H2IOSC MARKETPLACE

When a user requests the execution of a service (whether a single API or an application workflow), the MarketPlace manages the request by ensuring that:

- The service is executed in the correct runtime environment as defined in WSO2 Micro Integrator, complying with the configurations established by the service provider.
- The authentication and authorisation flow is verified, if necessary, through Keycloak, applying the security policies agreed upon between federated marketplaces. Alternatively, authentication credentials for a service can be incorporated into orchestration projects as parameterised environment variables.
- The invocation is controlled by WSO2 API Manager, which imposes any restrictions on the resources that can be consumed by the user.

Authentication and authorisation mechanisms

Keycloak can be used to manage certain levels of authentication within the H2IOSC MarketPlace. If the H2IOSC MarketPlace and the marketplace hosting the invoked service recognise each other as 'trusted' (thanks to a token exchange between their respective authentication systems), access to services could be managed without requiring additional user authentication, ensuring federated access between different marketplaces. Similarly, a single service could be allowed to request the MarketPlace Keycloak to verify the user's credentials.

The technical specifications have been defined in WP5 in collaboration with the external developer.

API usage monitoring and resource management

The H2IOSC MarketPlace is able to monitor the use of invoked APIs. This means that a service may only be accessible if it is called through the H2IOSC MarketPlace, allowing, for example, the bandwidth available to a user to be limited, the maximum number of executable requests to be adjusted, and custom access policies to be defined for specific users or groups.

These controls are implemented through the WSO2 API Manager, which allows you to define throttling and usage quota management policies. In this way, the MarketPlace can ensure fair use of available resources and prevent abuse of access to exposed services.

Thanks to the capabilities of WSO2 API Manager, the MarketPlace implements advanced execution monitoring tools, which allow users to check the status of their requests and receive notifications in case of errors or delays in workflow processing. WSO2 API Manager also tracks requests, providing detailed reports on service usage and execution efficiency, which can also be used by H2IOSC WP2 for its monitoring activities.

Asynchronous execution and response time management

Some services may require longer processing times or depend on processing distributed across multiple infrastructures. The H2IOSC MarketPlace supports asynchronous execution of API endpoints, ensuring that:

- Requests are routed correctly, even in the presence of high latency.
- Users can receive status notifications or callbacks upon completion of processing.
- Results are made available through user-configured storage systems.
- Integration with WSO2 Micro Integrator allows these asynchronous flows to be orchestrated, ensuring that each execution is managed efficiently and scalably.

4.6 OPERATIONAL SCENARIOS, USE CASES AND THEIR BENEFITS

The implementation of orchestration in the H2IOSC MarketPlace opens up the possibility of managing complex operational scenarios, offering users an integrated environment for accessing and combining digital services. One of the most significant scenarios involves textual analysis in the field of Digital Humanities. In this context, a user can design an application workflow that connects different text generation tools (e.g. from images through recognition, or by collating from multiple digital sources) and text processing and analysis tools, aggregating APIs and data exposed by multiple research infrastructures and/or other heterogeneous sources. This process allows linguistic, stylometric or philological analyses to be performed on a text corpus in an automated manner, texts and apparatus

to be organised, and publications to be prepared automatically or with assistance, ensuring greater interoperability between existing services throughout the research cycle and facilitating the reuse of data and methods. In this direction, a pilot meta-service federation focusing on the edition of manuscripts and texts of historical interest has been developed in H2IOSC.

A simpler concrete use case on which orchestration has been tested in the H2IOSC MarketPlace concerns communication between the two pilot services of Activities 7.10 and 7.11, namely the service of FAIRification and management of digital resource collections and the creation of digital editions of printed texts. Orchestration establishes an interaction flow between these two services, allowing the data generated by the first to be used directly by the second based on simple options and without the need for detailed manual intervention. The MarketPlace manages the invocation and transfer of data between the two platforms, ensuring that the process adheres to the access and security rules defined by the administrators of the systems involved.

The operating model and its benefits

The orchestration model represents a major step forward in ensuring the sharing of a consistent operating architecture among all stakeholders involved in supporting the federation.

The validation of the operational model was structured around the elements listed below. These elements paved the way for the development of orchestration guidelines based on the model's technical feasibility and alignment with both the common and specific needs of the Project's federated infrastructures.

- Confirmation of the separation between orchestration and runtime, to ensure that the MarketPlace does not take on direct computational loads.
- Definition of specifications for interoperability between federated marketplaces, including mutual authentication and token exchange mechanisms.
- Verification of application workflows, with the development and testing of orchestrations using WSO2 Micro Integrator.
- Progressive implementation of access monitoring and control to ensure that API management policies can be successfully applied.
- Validation of the model ensures that the architecture meets the project requirements and defines the terms under which it is shared by the federation.

The adoption of this orchestration model brings several benefits to the H2IOSC project and the research infrastructures involved, in particular:

- **Standardisation of access to services:** the use of WP6 manifests and WSO2 API Manager will ensure uniform API exposure, improving compatibility between infrastructures.
- **Ease of integration and scalability:** the MarketPlace will allow for the gradual integration of new services and infrastructures without substantial changes to the architecture.
- **Optimised resource management:** the implementation of throttling policies and usage quotas will prevent system overload and ensure fair distribution of resources.
- **Improved security:** Centralised access control and request tracking through the WSO2 Identity Server will increase data protection and system governance.

5. API ORCHESTRATION IN THE DIGITAL HUMANITIES

The business model for the use of API orchestrators can be transferred to the field of Digital Humanities (DH), where an API management and orchestration system can offer support for the analysis, creation, organisation and execution of projects that integrate data, text, images, and complex cultural models. Thanks to API orchestration, different data sources, analysis tools and distributed digital resources can be connected and made to talk to each other, thus facilitating the realisation of complex and interconnected projects (Sichera et al. 2024). Regarding **the H2IOSC project** in particular, this approach also addresses an **expressed need of** various research communities, as identified in the *landscaping* work conducted within the framework of the activities of **WP2 Landscaping and building communities** of the H2IOSC project⁸. Linguists, archaeologists and philosophers, for instance, complain about the fragmentation of the service offer and the multiplicity of infrastructures, and call for the strengthening and implementation of the existing ones by making them capable of aggregating and providing access to services, tools and resources through unambiguous and integrated access points and routes.

Consider, for instance, the case of **federated data repositories**, where APIs provide access to digital collections dispersed across different archives, libraries, museums, and universities. These repositories can be queried and combined via APIs, facilitating access to heterogeneous content such as historical documents, literary works, photo archives, and audio-visual materials. In this context, management via API orchestrators makes it possible to unify data access modes and to control authentication and access management according to the level of authorisation required for each dataset.

Another natural area of use is Text Mining and Natural Language Processing (NLP). With the use of **NLP APIs**, DH platforms can implement advanced analyses, such as entity extraction, identification of themes, concepts and *sentiments*, and creation of semantic networks. Orchestration makes it possible to automate sequences of textual transformations and analyses, by routing data through pipelines that include cleaning, normalisation, tokenisation, and in-depth analysis to produce structured outputs that can be used for further analysis or visualisation.

In mapping historical and cultural relationships, APIs can help integrate and orchestrate data from multiple sources in order to build complex *network analysis* models. For example, an API orchestrator can centralise and synchronise data from different archives to represent connections between authors, works, historical events, and cultural movements, allowing scholars to build dynamic and interactive visualisations. APIs can also facilitate integration through geo-referencing tools, enabling spatial analysis and the creation of interactive maps based on historical data to represent the movement and influence of events or personalities over time.

Sharing data and resources via APIs also supports the creation of **open ecosystems** where researchers, developers and the public can access tools and resources. Public APIs allow external developers and researchers to build custom applications, integrate data visualisation tools, and develop new analyses, increasing the scope and impact of available resources. API orchestrators facilitate permission and

⁸ <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/the-project/>.

security management, establishing access rules to protect sensitive data and regulating public access to resources.

In a comprehensive and heterogeneous framework such as H2IOSC, APIs can become crucial for the construction of **digital multimedia archives and editions** integrating text, images, video, and audio. Consider the need for simultaneous access to diverse multimedia materials that might be in physically or technically separate archives. APIs make it possible to aggregate these materials into a single access platform, while the API orchestrator manages the flow of requests, ensuring that the data is presented in a uniform manner and conforms to metadata and copyright management standards.

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7. ANNEXES

The deliverable is completed by the following **five Annexes**, which correspond to **objective, quantitative, and measurable indicators relevant to the monitoring and ex-post assessment of the expected results**.

As these are produced at the end of the project cycle, most of the Annexes predictably present **final versions of the outputs** (systems and services), some of which were released and presented at earlier stages of the Project's development.

In particular, **Annex 1** provides the **beta version of the service catalogue**, representing a more advanced stage compared to the alpha version presented in the Annex to deliverable D.5.1 - interim. This beta version has been solidified and finalised in the **final structure of the service catalogue in connection with the MarketPlace**, as set out in the following **Annex 2**.

Annex 5 also outlines the **final version of the recommendation system based on AI**, the alpha version of which was also presented in the Annex to deliverable D.5.1 - interim.

7.1 ANNEX 1

THE BETA VERSION OF THE CATALOGUE OF SERVICES

The initial list of services planned for the H2IOSC MarketPlace reflects the breadth and diversity of the **joint work of the RIs** participating in the Project.

During the initial phase, **the catalogue** collected the results of the service provision and remote deployment activities to be launched in WP6, as well as the initial experiments and prototypes to be developed within WP7.

The aim was to provide a highly representative **overview of the skills, technologies, and resources that the project partners intended to make available to the scientific and cultural community**.

The following table shows the **beta version of the Data & digital services catalogue updated as of October 31, 2025**. This version is not final, but it was tested and evaluated by a select group of project experts. As reported in D 1.4 H2IOSC offers, in addition to and in combination with digital services, also training and technical services (described in the mentioned document).

Key activities	Description "Standard service"- no fee or contribution
[E-RIHS] IMATI GE - GRAVIFIX tool. It can be applied to single closed objects represented as triangle meshes, which needs simplification and/or cleaning.	The GRAVIFIX tool can be applied to single closed objects (or a dataset of single objects) represented as triangle meshes, which needs simplification and/or cleaning (solving geometric or topological errors).

<p>[E-RIHS] IMATI GE – 3D ANNOTATION tool. It allows associating textual tags to parts of 3D models, represented as triangular meshes. The textual tags derive from a controlled vocabulary and are used to annotate areas, lines and points of a 3D mesh, which have an interest for the user.</p>	<p>The 3D annotation tool allows associating textual tags to parts of 3D models, represented as triangular meshes. The textual tags derive from a controlled vocabulary and are used to annotate areas, lines and points of a 3D mesh, which have an interest for the user.</p>
<p>[E-RIHS] IMATI GE – SimilarityLib. The toolkit contains a number of functions for evaluating geometric characteristics, building descriptors and computing similarity distances and their combination. It contains the routines to elaborate a number of geometric properties.</p>	<p>This Toolkit contains a number of functions for evaluating geometric characteristics, building descriptors and computing similarity distances and their combination. In the standard mode, it contains the routines to elaborate a number of geometric properties: area, volume, mean curvature, shape index, shape diameter function, minimal bounding box, thickness, RGB to Cielab coordinates conversion; descriptors: compactness, Non normalized shape distributions, histograms, persistence diagrams; similarity distances: L1, LP, Earth Mover’s distance, Bhattacharya distance, matching distance; and the combination of several distances.</p>
<p>[E-RIHS] ISPC CT - AI/ML solutions for analysis and visualization of Multimodal Datasets.</p>	<p>Activity performed under the open calls of the Digital platform of E-RIHS.</p>
<p>[E-RIHS] ISPC CT - Remotization: Hy-Molab platform.</p>	<p>Activity performed under the open calls of the Molab platform of E-RIHS.</p>
<p>[E-RIHS] ISPC NA/RM - ATON (WebXR services for HS). A plug&play platform based on open-source ATON framework to accelerate the development and deployment of custom, cross-device and interoperable Web3D/WebXR applications targeting Heritage field.</p>	<p>Standard service offers access to many features. Restrictions include storage, some advanced features, and private scenes to encourage openness and model spread. Support is provided only with the documentation on the website.</p>

<p>[E-RIHS] ISPC RM - Kapto. A service to track and record interactive sessions performed using remote devices, infrastructures, public exhibits or online web-applications.</p>	<p>Standard service allows to track and record interactive sessions with custom attributes; base data cleaning and filtering; with minor limitations on duration per-record and storage.</p>
<p>[E-RIHS] ISPC LE - SENNSE (Spatial hEritage scieNce oNline Sensor Environment) Wireless sensor networks for cultural heritage conservation and monitoring.</p>	<p>Design, development, and management of wireless sensor networks to meet the needs of the sites to monitor and the requirements of the institutions/organizations that manage the site.</p>
<p>[E-RIHS] ISTI PI - Digital Fabrication Laboratory Virtual Access</p>	<p>This service allows virtual access to ISTI-PI Digital Fabrication Laboratory to facilitate researchers in obtaining physical replicas from their digital models.</p>
<p>[E-RIHS] INO FI - The Digital Twin, which will enclose the data from the multi-analytical analysis of an artwork, the metadata and a set of information from different datasets, will be made available to the heritage science community.</p>	<p>The platform developed by INO for the digital twin will enclose two case studies: a nearly flat object and a real three-dimensional one. The latter will be developed in close connection with WP7 as the output data of the pilot will feed the digital twin.</p>
<p>[DARIAH] OVI FI - TLIO</p>	<p>It is a search engine and web interface developed at the Institute of the CNR Opera del Vocabolario Italiano designed for consulting the TLIO (Tesoro della Lingua Italiana delle Origini). It furnishes an interactive graphical user interface that empowers users to explore the first historical dictionary of ancient Italian, born directly online.</p>
<p>[DARIAH] OVI FI - Pluto</p>	<p>It is an online system currently under development at the Institute of the CNR Opera del Vocabolario Italiano to provide access to the BTV (Bibliografia dei Testi Volgari), which represents the most extensive collection of bibliographic data on ancient Italian. Pluto aims for the gradual integration of all resources and tools related to TLIO into an integrated system, bringing together within a single platform databases and applications previously managed by separate systems.</p>

[DARIAH] OVI FI - GATTO	<p>GATTO (Gestione degli Archivi Testuali del Tesoro delle Origini) is a lexicographic software designed and developed by Domenico Iorio-Fili at the OVI. This software was born as a tool aimed at building, managing and querying the corpus of texts that is the basis of the Historical Dictionary of the Italian Language, developed by the OVI. More generally, GATTO allows lexicographic research to be carried out on a generic textual archive provided that the texts, suitably coded, are available on file together with the relevant bibliographic data.</p> <p>Available online at http://gattoweb.ovi.cnr.it.</p>
[DARIAH] OVI FI - TIGRO	<p>TIGRO is a reimagining and upgrading of the GATTO software with modern software tools, under active development at OVI. It aims to assist in the building and querying of general corpora of texts, with a specific focus on interoperability with existing standards and external services.</p>
[DARIAH] OVI FI - Mirabile, Archivio digitale della cultura medievale	<p>MIRABILE is a knowledge management system for the study and research on medieval culture promoted by the <i>Società Internazionale per lo Studio del Medioevo Latino</i> and the <i>Fondazione Ezio Franceschini</i> of Florence.</p> <p>Available online at https://www.mirabileweb.it.</p>
[DARIAH] OVI FI - EVT, Edition Visualization Technology	<p>A lightweight, open-source tool specifically designed to create digital editions from XML-encoded texts, freeing the scholar from the burden of web programming and enabling the final user to browse, explore and study digital editions by means of a user-friendly interface. Supports critical editions with complex critical apparatuses. Developed by a varied team based at the University of Pisa under the guide of Professor Roberto Rosselli Del Turco.</p>
[DARIAH] OVI FI - RAISE	<p>RAISE, a spin-off of the RESTORE project, is a collection of tools for data ingestion, semantization, storage and visualization. Its main components are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A set of command-line tools to assist data managers in the tasks such as data ingestion, filtering, cleaning, semantization; - A triple store (an instance of Openlink Virtuoso) enriched with custom APIs for data storage and querying; - A modular, customizable web-based GUI for data visualization. <p>See http://dev.restore.ovi.cnr.it:3000/TEAMOVI.</p>

<p>[DARIAH] OVI FI - TRAME: Text and manuscript transmission of the Middle Ages in Europe.</p>	<p>TRAME is a research infrastructure for medieval manuscripts. The TRAME engine scans a set of sources for searched terms and retrieves links to a wide range of possible information, from simple reference, to detailed manuscript records, to full-text transcriptions.</p>
<p>[DARIAH] OVI-FI - MFE: MetaFAIR Ecosystem</p>	<p>Platform for the integrated management of digitised manuscripts. Designed for researchers, scholars, and institutions such as libraries, archives and museums, it enables them to catalogue, preserve and enhance documents in a unified environment. Key features: Cataloguing, Digitisation, Digital Preservation, Access and use, Integration.</p>
<p>[OPERAS] Remote Open Access to content-based services and resources.</p>	<p>The service will allow the remote, non-real-time and possibly disconnected use of the resources, services and hubs (not necessarily only those developed by OPERAS) within the H2IOSC project, in connection with the workflow system of the H2IOSC MarketPlace.</p>
<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - LexO ItAnt - REST (micro)services for editing lexical data encoded in RDF/Turtle</p>	<p>LexO ItAnt is a service for querying dictionaries in RDF format, it interacts with a graphdb instance and is integrated within the EpiLexO interface of the ItAnt project. It is callable via HTTP calls through the use of REST APIs.</p>
<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - CASH ItAnt - REST (micro)services for managing and annotating TEI-EpiDoc documents.</p>	<p>CASH ItAnt is a suite of RESTful (micro)services designed for the management and annotation of TEI-EpiDoc documents. This system enables efficient processing of structured textual data, supporting advanced workflows for digital philology and linguistic annotation within the CLARIN-IT infrastructure. It provides tools for manipulating, annotating, and validating TEI-EpiDoc encoded texts, ensuring interoperability and facilitating scholarly research in the digital humanities.</p>
<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service - A tool for publishing and exploring controlled vocabularies encoded in SKOS.</p>	<p>SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service is a web-based tool designed for publishing and exploring controlled vocabularies encoded in SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System). It provides an intuitive interface for browsing, searching, and visualizing hierarchical or associative relationships between concepts, supporting knowledge organization and semantic interoperability in digital humanities and other domains.</p>

<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Triple Store - A graph database for storing semantic datasets (LLOD).</p>	<p>Triple Store is a graph database solution, powered by GraphDB, designed for storing and managing semantic datasets, particularly those adhering to the Linguistic Linked Open Data (LLOD) principles. It enables efficient querying, integration, and visualization of interconnected semantic data, supporting advanced research in linguistics and digital humanities through robust RDF and SPARQL functionalities.</p>
<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - EpiLexO ItAnt - interfaces for editing, querying, visualising linked language resources for ancient languages.</p>	<p>EpiLexO ItAnt provides interfaces for editing, querying, and visualizing linked language resources specifically tailored for ancient languages. This platform supports the management of linguistic data, enabling researchers to create, explore, and analyze interlinked lexical and textual resources, fostering digital philology and the study of ancient languages within a linked data framework.</p>
<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Stanza NLP Chain (Lemmatization, Dependency Parsing, NER for the Italian Language).</p>	<p>Stanza NLP Chain is a natural language processing pipeline designed for the Italian language, offering lemmatization, dependency parsing, and named entity recognition (NER). Built on the Stanza framework, this tool provides state-of-the-art linguistic analysis capabilities, supporting advanced research and applications in computational linguistics and language technology.</p>
<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint Data.</p>	<p>Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint Data is a tailored natural language processing pipeline designed to process and analyze parliamentary corpora encoded in the ParlaMint framework. Utilizing Stanza's robust capabilities, it supports tasks such as lemmatization, dependency parsing, and named entity recognition (NER), enabling detailed linguistic and semantic analysis of structured political discourse data.</p>
<p>[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - eScriptorium</p>	<p>eScriptorium is a platform for Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) developed by the Scripta research team at PSL (Paris Sciences et Lettres University). Its features include layout analysis, automated transcription, manual transcription, model training, and the import/export of images and transcriptions. Most of its services are also accessible via a REST API.</p>

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - EpiLexO Editor	EpiLexo Editor is an interface for creating lexica for epigraphic languages conformant to Semantic Web principles, linked to their testimonies (encoded in TEI-EpiDoc) and related bibliographies. The EpiLexO Editor operates upon a set of independent software backend components, mainly the LexO-server and the CASH-server. The application is designed to facilitate collaboration among scholars, enabling multiple researchers to work simultaneously on the same datasets in cooperation. The interface can be considered a functional working prototype, with core functionalities for lexicon processing, creation, and lookup implemented. The interface supports basic editing and creation of linked language resources for ancient languages.
[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - UDPipe	UDPipe is a trainable pipeline for tokenization, tagging, lemmatization and dependency parsing of CoNLL-U files. UDPipe is language-agnostic and can be trained given annotated data in CoNLL-U format. Trained models are provided for nearly all UD treebanks.
[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Named Entity Recognition (based on NameTag).	NameTag is an open-source tool for named entity recognition (NER). NameTag identifies proper names in text and classifies them into predefined categories, such as names of persons, locations, organizations, etc.
[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Federated Content Search.	The Federated Content Search (FCS) of CLARIN enables unified searching across distributed language resources and tools via a single interface. It connects diverse repositories using standardized protocols, allowing researchers to efficiently access, query, and analyze multilingual and multimodal language data. This system fosters resource discovery and interdisciplinary research in linguistics and the humanities.
[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - TEI Publisher + eXist-db.	TEI Publisher is a platform for publishing and exploring TEI-encoded texts through interactive and customizable web interfaces. It simplifies the process of transforming TEI XML into user-friendly online presentations, making complex text data accessible for digital humanities projects. eXist-db is an open-source XML database optimized for storing, querying, and managing XML data. It powers applications like TEI Publisher by providing robust indexing, search, and transformation capabilities, making it ideal for projects centered on structured text and digital editions.

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Text Aligner	Word alignment is the task of identifying words in a source (part of) text that correspond to words in a target (part of) text, given the sentences are in same relationships of each other. The word alignment services aim to improve textual transmission, textual collation, and translation. Possible implementation: string2string library and Bertalign.
Interlumo (task 7.7 - Immersive Analytics and Spatial Interfaces). A modular suite to capture, analyze and inspect remote interactive sessions.	Standard service offers access to full pipeline including: 1) Track and record interactive sessions using custom attributes, with minor limitations on duration and storage; 2) base data cleaning on captured records and 3) Base inspection for 3D environments with immersive analytics toolkit via Aton service.
7.10a Design, development and implementation of a fairification workflow for the contents of the H2IOSC project and realisation, starting from data and documents in non-FAIR form, of a set of semantic resources fairified according to the same workflow, ready to be uploaded on the H2IOSC platform; release of a pilot project in the form of a proof-of-concept for the verification of the compliance of data with the FAIR principles (FAIRness) of specific datasets.	Service for verifying the FAIRness of datasets.
7.10b Development of a web application for the management of multi-tenant and multi-user digital libraries where each digital library is composed of heterogeneous collections of data and open access resources, mediated by specialised viewers, metadata and data search functions, and ancillary services useful to enhance the search and consultation experience (annotations, bookmarks, private collections, etc.)	Tool for transcribing printed texts; tool for managing data collections (bibliographical, lexicographical, biographical, textual).

<p>7.5. Design and development of a VRE for illuminated manuscripts investigated by analytical methods. The virtual space will provide the access to the manuscript archive and a set of tools for data exchange, analysis, integration and visualization.</p>	
<p>7.5 HeriVerse-Heritage Science Metaverse The pilot aims to create a three-dimensional immersive space based on a graph of knowledge that acts as a container for information. Within the 3D space there are simplified geometric shapes called proxies which, if selected, query the knowledge graph, calling up the information associated with the geometry itself. The pilot will use a number of tools and services (based on open standards) distributed at E-RIHS nodes, available to the scientific community, enabling researchers and professionals to collaborate remotely in real time.</p>	

<p>7.5 Platform "SENSE" (Spatial heritage science online Sensor Environment) Design, development and implementation of an open source hardware/software platform that allows the analysis, post-processing and presentation of a wide range of data (microenvironmental, structural, energy, geolocated) from the scientific domain of cultural heritage. Data will be provided by the Wireless Sensor Network management middleware platform (developed under WP6.8) via calls to its APIs and presented through multi-tenant interactive and customizable dashboards.</p> <p>The component will enable the storage and linking of georeferenced data in investigated contexts, the artifacts studied and the analytical analyses carried out on them to produce new knowledge through integrated data analysis making the data accessible and shareable.</p>	<p>Analysis, post processing and visualization of a wide range of data (micro-environmental, structural, energy, geolocated data) of the scientific domain of cultural heritage acquired through wireless sensor networks (WSN) configured on the platform (network layer features of the SENSE platform developed in WP6 task 6.8).</p> <p>The features for registered users to configure their networks and their dashboards as long as they make the acquired data freely usable or in aggregated form.</p>
<p>7.11 DSE publishing platform</p>	<p>Final stage of DSE (Digital Scholarly Editions) creation: it allows to connect production to final publication. Devised on the example of a digital edition of Vico's New Science, it offers a set of tailorable models of edition.</p>
<p>7.11 Platform for the publication and scientific validation of grey literature.</p>	<p>Open dissemination of grey literature in a journal-like format, accompanied by an overlay journal. It is based on open software under a common interface layer for access and process governance.</p>
<p>7.4 Open Digital Archaeology Hub. Open platform for the discovering of Digital Archaeology resources, tools, and methods (with <i>Archeologia e Calcolatori's</i> repository as case study).</p>	<p>Open Digital Archaeology Hub:</p> <p>1) Open access to the online catalogue of the Open Digital Epigraphy Hub, which lists and describes online resources (datasets, articles, images, projects) concerning Digital Archaeology, currently aggregated from <i>Archeologia e Calcolatori</i>, A&C_IADI, and DHeLO archives; 2) access to the search functionalities of the catalogue's content, including webGIS browsing A&C case study: 1) Open access to the online catalogues of A&C and A&C_IADI articles and images (https://www.archcalc.cnr.it/; https://iadi.archcalc.cnr.it/), 2)</p>

	access to the related APIs, 3) access to A&C OAI-PMH repository, 4) access to the BiDiAr Zotero group library (https://www.zotero.org/groups/5293298/bidiar).
7.4 Open Digital Epigraphy Hub. Open platform for the discovering of resources, tools, and methods in the field of Digital Epigraphy (with DASI as case study).	Open Digital Epigraphy Hub: 1) Open access to the online catalogue of the Open Digital Epigraphy Hub, which lists and describes online resources published worldwide and related to Digital Epigraphy, 2) access to the search functionality of the catalogue's content; 3) access to the catalogue's API; 4) access to the Hub's bibliographic references collection for metadata consultation and download; 5) access to the related Zotero group library. DASI (https://dasi.cnr.it) case study: 1) Open access to the archive's contents (epigraphic texts with metadata, support, provenance and bibliographic information), 2) access to word lists and search functionalities, 3) access to the OAI-PMH repository (EpiDoc, oai_dc, EDM), 4) access to the API, 5) access to the "CSAI" (one of DASI's corpora) Zotero group library (https://www.zotero.org/groups/5280688/csai).
7.3 Digital Philology Hub	Provide a digital environment with a complete set of tools to create and manage digital scholarly editions. Main services: 1) loading and multiplatform research of mss (including metadata and images where available); 2) loading mss transcription or HTR; 3) assisted collation 4) varia lectio, glossary, apparatus, to complete a critical edition; 5) permanent storage of the produced output, up to and including the full critical edition.
7.3 Digital Heritage and Memory Hub	Providing a digital environment with a complete set of tools for a comprehensive study and analysis of the tangible component of mss. and other cultural heritage artifacts.
E-RIHS MOLAB-FIXLAB (7.6 painting collection hub) Access to laboratory instruments for mechanochemical measurements of micro-samples/stratigraphic sections (SCITEC-PG).	Access to the experimental facility for research collaborative projects enriching/feeding the digital hub for painting collections. Experimental data MUST be included in the painting collection hub contents.
E-RIHS MOLAB-FIXLAB (7.6 painting collection hub) Access to spectral data, hyperspectral imaging and art historical data of paintings and polychrome objects (SCITEC-PG).	Access to the available contents of the painting collection hub.

<p>E-RIHS MOLAB-FIXLAB (7.6 painting collection hub) Access workstations (DELL PRECISION) for analysis of spectral data with data processing including chemometry and machine learning approaches (Python and RStudio environments) (SCITEC-PG).</p>	<p>Access to the digital facilities for research collaborative projects enriching/feeding the digital hub for painting collections. Outcomes of the analytical digital facilities MUST be included in the painting collection hub contents.</p>
<p>Prototyping platform for Virtual / Physical Exhibitions (Task 7.9) a) possibility to autonomously configure ready-to-use prototypes of 3D interactive and collaborative web – experiences b) facilitating collaborative design of Virtual / Physical exhibitions (ISPC-UO-FI).</p>	<p>The tool is provided as is, as a self-hosted opensource solution inheriting ATON licences (GPL-3).</p>
<p>7.2 Implementation of the dedicated Speech and Oral archives platform which offers FAIR deposit and exploitation of various archives according to the best practices and needs of different communities. Building on the experience of the Archivio Vi.Vo. regional project and of similar initiatives developed in CLARIN-IT. The platform will be integrated with advanced functionalities to preserve, describe/annotate, make accessible, enrich, query Oral archives and related documents. We will pilot this platform also for fostering oral archives musealisation in collaboration with the Cultural Heritage RIs.</p>	<p>The service is aimed at providing a platform for preservation and promotion of oral archives. The platform provides two interfaces with functionalities to deposit the conservative copy and to access the documentary unit.</p>
<p>7.2 Offering the possibility to users to publish language resources (with an open license) in a triple store (and make those resources available and queryable via a SPARQL endpoint) as part of the workflow for depositing those resources in the ILC4CLARIN repository; assistance for users in creating RDF datasets, including the provision of training</p>	<p>The service provides users with the capability to publish language resources under an open license in a triple store. These resources are made available and queryable through a SPARQL endpoint. This feature is integrated as part of the workflow for depositing language resources into the ILC4CLARIN repository. Additionally, the service includes access to a vocabulary platform (SKOSMOS), which offers a wide range of thesauri and vocabularies in the SSH domain, freely accessible to the entire community.</p>

<p>materials, and python libraries and tools for converting data into RDF and data-cleaning. A vocabulary platform (SKOSMOS) for making useful thesauri and vocabularies (in SKOS) in the SSH domain available to the whole community.</p>	
<p>7.2 Development of a framework to manage and administer multimodal psycholinguistic tasks on desktop and mobile devices.</p> <p>Psycho-linguistic tasks that can be developed as plug-ins, based on an interface protocol defined by the framework itself.</p> <p>The framework will be responsible for the insertion and modification of users, measurement campaigns and trials (which associate a user to a measurement campaign and one or more tasks) and, during the execution of trials, the collection of general information (client device information, status change schedule, interface events, audio streams, video streams). Other "task-specific" data are collected by the task itself and sent to the framework after execution.</p> <p>The framework must be equipped with a "remote control" system so that it can send commands to the other running instances.</p> <p>Each instance of the framework checks for and executes queued remote commands.</p> <p>When the trial is running, remote command control and execution is the responsibility of the task.</p>	<p>This pilot is a framework designed for managing and administering multimodal psycholinguistic tasks on both desktop and mobile devices. It supports tasks such as lexical decisions, questionnaires, puzzles, and text-reading, which are treated as modular plug-ins following a predefined protocol. The framework handles user data, both static and longitudinal, organizes measurement campaigns, and manages trials by linking users, campaigns, and tasks with specific settings. Its modular design ensures flexibility and scalability, making it a powerful tool for psycholinguistic research and experimentation.</p>

<p>7.8 Cultural Heritage Pilot (E-RIHS): Scientific digital hub for metal artworks.</p>	<p>Access to the experimental facility for collaborative research projects enriching/feeding the digital hub for metal collections. Experimental data to be included in the metal collection hub contents.</p>
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7.2 ANNEX 2

THE FINAL STRUCTURE OF THE CATALOGUE OF SERVICES IN CONNECTION WITH THE PROJECT MARKETPLACE

The **list of services offered through the H2IOSC Marketplace** represents the **joint outcome** of the collaborative efforts undertaken in **WP6**, which focused on servicing and remotely deploying existing tools, and **WP7**, which centred on demonstrating new application pilots, as well as technical and training services.

WP6 involved transforming the tools and functionalities developed by the various infrastructures into remotely accessible web services, while WP7 developed new pilot platforms for specific interdisciplinary research scenarios. Both constitute the category of **Data & Digital services** which are, indeed, software, tools, datasets, and pilot projects addressing the needs of those involved in the study, management, and valorization of cultural, linguistic, and historical heritage, including tools for remote monitoring, diagnostics, data extraction and analysis, and digital fabrication.

In addition, the catalogue contains **Technical Services** which include digital infrastructures essential for research and data management, including solutions for secure storage, high-performance computing, AI-powered content analysis, and advanced ICT services to support processing, sharing, and interoperability of data within virtual and collaborative research environments and **Training Services**, i.e. free self-paced courses and platforms for sharing and downloading open-access training materials, tailored for people involved in the humanities, social sciences, and heritage science, to strengthen interdisciplinary skills and the use of Research Infrastructures.

More broadly the **service catalogue** leverages and optimises the **strong interconnection** between the **four RIs**, with their associated **services**, and the **MarketPlace**.

The beta version was an experimental release made available to a select group of users for testing and feedback; this version, however, represents the expected **final composition of the service catalogue**.

Data & Digital services updated as of October 31, 2025

[E-RIHS] IMATI GE - GRAVIFIX tool. It can be applied to single closed objects represented as triangle meshes, that require simplification and/or cleaning.

[E-RIHS] IMATI GE – 3D ANNOTATION tool. It allows associating textual tags to parts of 3D models, represented as triangular meshes. The textual tags derive from a controlled vocabulary and are used to annotate areas, lines and points of a 3D mesh, that are of interest to the user.

[E-RIHS] IMATI GE – SimilarityLib. The toolkit contains a number of functions for evaluating geometric characteristics, building descriptors and computing similarity distances and their combination. It contains the routines to elaborate a number of geometric properties.

[E-RIHS] ISPC CT - AI/ML solutions for analysis and visualization of Multimodal Datasets.

[E-RIHS] ISPC CT - Remotization: HyMolab platform.

[E-RIHS] ISPC NA/RM - WebXR services for Heritage Science. A plug&play architecture offered by open-source ATON framework to accelerate the development and deployment of custom, cross-device and interoperable Web3D/WebXR applications targeting Heritage field.

[E-RIHS] ISPC RM - Capture services. A set of services to track and record interactive sessions performed using remote devices, infrastructures, public exhibits or online web-applications.

[E-RIHS] ISPC LE - SENSE: Wireless sensor networks for cultural heritage conservation and monitoring.

[E-RIHS] ISTI PI - Digital Fabrication Laboratory Virtual Access – WP 6.4.

[E-RIHS] INO FI - The Digital Twin, which will enclose the data from the multi-analytical analysis of an artwork, the metadata and a set of information from different datasets, will be made available to the heritage science community.

[DARIAH] OVI FI - TIGRO

[DARIAH] OVI FI - EVT, Edition Visualization Technology.

[DARIAH] OVI FI - RAISE

[DARIAH] OVI FI - MFE - MetaFair Ecosystem.

[OPERAS] Remote Open Access to content-based services and resources. A pluggable distribution system that will ensure the remote use of the resources, services and hubs implemented by OPERAS within the H2IOSC project and, more generally, their remote, non real-time and possibly disconnected use.

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - LexO ItAnt - REST (micro)services for editing lexical data encoded in RDF/Turtle.

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - CASH ItAnt - REST (micro)services for managing and annotating TEI-EpiDoc documents.

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service - A tool for publishing and exploring controlled vocabularies encoded in SKOS.

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Triple Store - A graph database for storing semantic datasets (LLOD).

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - EpiLexO ItAnt - interfaces for editing, querying, visualising linked language resources for ancient languages.

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Stanza NLP Chain (Lemmatization, Dependency Parsing, NER for the Italian Language)

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint Data

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Italian Dialogues by Giordano Bruno

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Corpus delle Opere di S.Teresa de Ávila (ILC PI)

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Vittorio Alfieri's tragedies

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Cretan Institutional Inscriptions

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - LMF ML Merger

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - LMF Merger

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - SCF Extractor (IT) and language independent

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Multiword Extractor(s)

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Desr web service

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Freeling-IT

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - It-Sr-NER

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Tokenizers and pos tagger services from PANACEA and OPENER.

[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - eScriptorium

7.7 Interluo (Immersive Analytics and Spatial Interfaces)

7.10a Design, development and implementation of a fairification workflow for the contents of the H2IOSC project and realisation, starting from data and documents in non-FAIR form, of a set of semantic resources fairified according to the same workflow, ready to be uploaded on the H2IOSC platform; release of a pilot project in the form of a proof-of-concept for the verification of the compliance of data with the FAIR principles (FAIRness) of specific datasets. The result of this activity will provide an initial core of datasets available in the MarketPlace catalogue.

7.10b Development of a web application for the management of multi-tenant and multi-user digital libraries where each digital library is composed of heterogeneous collections of data and open access resources, mediated by specialised viewers, metadata and data search functions, and ancillary services useful to enhance the search and consultation experience (annotations, bookmarks, private collections, etc.).

7.5. Design and development of a VRE for illuminated manuscripts investigated by analytical methods. The virtual space will provide the access to the manuscript archive and a set of tools for data exchange, analysis, integration and visualization.

7.5 HeriVerse-Heritage Science Metaverse

The pilot aims to create a three-dimensional immersive space based on a graph of knowledge that acts as a container for information. Within the 3D space there are simplified geometric shapes called proxies which, if selected, query the knowledge graph, calling up the information associated with the geometry itself.

The pilot will use a number of tools and services (based on open standards) distributed at E-RIHS nodes, available to the scientific community, enabling researchers and professionals to collaborate remotely in real time.

7.5 Platform "SENENSE" (Spatial hERitage scieNce oNline Sensor Environment)

Design, development and implementation of an open source hardware/software platform that allows the analysis, post-processing and presentation of a wide range of data (microenvironmental, structural, energy, geolocalized) from the scientific domain of cultural heritage. Data will be provided by the Wireless Sensor Network management middleware platform (developed under WP6.8) via calls to its APIs and presented through multi-tenant interactive and customizable dashboards.

The component will enable the storage and linking of georeferenced data in investigated contexts, the artifacts studied and the analytical analyses carried out on them to produce new knowledge through integrated data analysis making the data accessible and shareable.

7.11 DSE publishing platform

7.11 Platform for the publication and scientific validation of grey literature

7.4 Open Digital Archaeology Hub. Open platform for the discovering of Digital Archaeology resources, tools, and methods.

7.4 Open Digital Epigraphy Hub. Open platform for the discovering of resources, tools, and methods in the field of Digital Epigraphy.

7.3 Digital Philology Hub

MFE - MetaFair Ecosystem

7.3 Digital Heritage and Memory Hub

E-RIHS MOLAB-FIXLAB (7.6 painting collection hub) Access to laboratory instruments for mechano-chemical measurements of micro-samples/stratigraphic sections (SCITEC-PG).

E-RIHS MOLAB-FIXLAB (7.6 painting collection hub) Access to spectral data, hyperspectral imaging and art historical data of paintings and polychrome objects (SCITEC-PG).

E-RIHS MOLAB-FIXLAB (7.6 painting collection hub) Access workstations (DELL PRECISION) for analysis of spectral data with data processing including chemometry and machine learning approaches (Python and RStudio environments) (SCITEC-PG).

7.2 Implementation of the dedicated Speech and Oral archives platform which offers FAIR deposit and exploitation of various archives according to the best practices and needs of different communities. Building on the experience of the Archivio Vi.Vo. regional project and of similar initiatives developed in CLARIN-IT. The platform will be integrated with advanced functionalities to preserve, describe/annotate, make accessible, enrich, query oral archives and related documents. We will pilot this platform also for fostering oral archives musealisation in collaboration with the Cultural Heritage RIs.

7.2 Offering the possibility to users to publish language resources (with an open licence) in a triple store (and make those resources available and queryable via a SPARQL endpoint) as part of the workflow for depositing those resources in the ILC4CLARIN repository; assistance for users in creating RDF datasets, including the provision of training materials, and Python libraries and tools for converting data into RDF and data-cleaning. A vocabulary platform (SKOSMOS) for making useful thesauri and vocabularies (in SKOS) in the SSH domain available to the whole community.

7.2 Development of a framework to manage and administer multimodal psycholinguistic tasks on desktop and mobile devices.

Psycho-linguistic tasks that can be developed as plug-ins, based on an interface protocol defined by the framework itself.

The framework will be responsible for the insertion and modification of users, measurement campaigns and trials (which associate a user to a measurement campaign and one or more tasks) and, during the execution of trials, the collection of general information (client device information, status change schedule, interface events, audio streams, video streams). Other "task-specific" data are collected by the task itself and sent to the framework after execution.

The framework must be equipped with a "remote control" system so that it can send commands to the other running instances. Each instance of the framework checks for and executes queued remote commands. When the trial is running, remote command control and execution is the responsibility of the task.

7.8 Cultural Heritage Pilot (E-RIHS): Scientific digital hub for metal artworks

7.9 Prototyping platform for Virtual / Physical Exhibitions: Development of a web-based tool to design Virtual / Physical exhibitions supporting co-design activities, configuring and simulating functional prototypes. The framework allows multidisciplinary teams to visualise in 3d the space of the exhibition, introduce physical and graphical elements, combine contents and interactions using prebuilt and extendible modules.

The tool will provide customizable templates for relevant approaches in cultural dissemination and virtual simulations, providing solutions for navigating and exploring 3D spaces and artworks (e.g. Museums' Digital Twin) and configuring guided experiences (as task-oriented activities in multi-user sessions).

Technical services updated as of October 31, 2025

Services	Brief description
Federated Cloud Service (IAAS)	Management and hosting of the general infrastructure of the H2IOSC federation, including the MarketPlace, the federated Authentication service and interoperability services coordinating the RIs (common semantic framework ontologies, etc.); Management of the RI-level dedicated platforms (Digilab, AEON, ...).
Trusted storage (SAAS)	Storage service for the MarketPlace and the RI Platforms as well as for services defined in WP6 and Pilots and related service defined in WP7

High Capacity Computing (CAAS)	HPC for computationally-intensive tasks for services and applications defined in WP6 and Pilots and related service defined in WP7 (3d rendering and other complex image processing, semantic data services, querying of large datasets...).
AI based/supported services (LLM training, HTR, NLP other)	AI services for specific tasks for the applications and tools offered in WP6 and developed in WP7 (AI-based NLP, HTR, others).
Other ICT services (hosting etc.)	Hosting of applications, services and pilots defined as part of WP6 and WP7.
INFRA HELP-DESK	Limited support (through tickets and so on) offered to partners of the participating RIs for use of the offered services, Pilots, the RI Platforms and the Marketplace.
Cyber security	All systems and stored data will have state-of-the-art and continually maintained and upgraded protection from digital attacks, damage, or unauthorized access.
Operating Systems Management	Centrally controlling and automating the lifecycle of server operating systems—including provisioning, patching, configuration, performance tuning, security hardening, and monitoring.

Training services updated as of October 31, 2025

Services	Brief description
H2IOSC Training Environment	The platform allows users to: enroll in courses by accessing a large catalogue of courses, structured to meet the needs of students, professionals and, organizations; manage your page with an intuitive dashboard that allows you to monitor progress, consult teaching materials and, access certifications obtained; and interact with the community thanks to collaborative tools such as forums, chats and, virtual working groups, where users can exchange ideas, solve problems and, create learning networks.
H2IOSC Training Library	The H2IOSC Training Library platform is a repository designed for the deposit and storage of reusable teaching material for teachers and trainers. Teachers and trainers will be able to publish their own teaching products, attributing a Persistent Identifier, a Creative Commons licence and a standard citation, improving visibility and reusability. The platform will provide a means of

	discovery and reuse the teaching material, to facilitate the work of teachers who are engaged in the didactic design of a course.
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7.3 ANNEX 3

UX TESTING OF THE PLATFORM - SYSTEM VALIDATION AND ACCEPTANCE PLAN

The following **test plan** fully exploits the **user experience** and is designed to optimise it.

Serving as a **complete roadmap for testing**, it ensures a consistent process by defining clear objectives, target users, specific tasks, and the methodology for collecting and analysing data to identify areas for system refinement and improvement.

The verification activities described below will be completed by April 15, 2026.

The ultimate goal is to create **a more effective and user-friendly MarketPlace** that meets users' needs and expectations, and efficiently solves their problems.

Introduction

PURPOSE

This report outlines the MarketPlace platform's **integration and verification process**.

The main stages of the system design and implementation process (requirements, specifications, design, and code) are subject to testing and continuous technical reviews. The aim of these reviews is to verify the system's completeness, correctness, and adherence to requirements, specifications, standards, and regulations. The different types of testing are as follows:

- **Unit tests:** aimed at verifying adherence to the programming specifications from the logical point of view of the module/service;
- **Integration tests:** focus on ensuring that the various components and subsystems of an application are built and made available in the correct way;
- **System tests:** verify the correct execution of the entire application, as well as its interoperability with other applications. Functional, usability, performance, reliability, load, and security tests are carried out during this phase;
- **Acceptance test:** performed to verify that the final system meets the intended needs and conforms to the defined requirements and design specifications.

The following table shows how project documents and validation documents are related:

Validation Process Documentation				
	Customer Requirements	Design Architecture	System specifications	Code
Testing documentation	Acceptance Test Plan Acceptance Test Procedures Test Report Matrix	Integration Test	System Test	Unit Test

SCOPE

This plan outlines the verification activities that will be carried out to validate the WP5 MarketPlace platform of the H2IOSC project. These activities will involve all the underlying systems and will verify the usability of the user interfaces and the performance of the software developed by the vendor company.

DEFINITIONS, ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Meaning
BO	Back-Office
FE	Front-End
BE	Back-End
H2IOSC	Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud
FT_BO_functionality_name	Test Functionality_Back Office_functionality_name
TC_BO_Test_name	Test_case_Back Office_Test_name
FT_FE_functionality_name	Test Functionality_Front End_functionality_name
TC_FE_Test_name	Test_case_Front_End_Test_name
FT_BE_functionality_name	Test Functionality_Back End_functionality_name
TC_BE_Test_name	Test_case_Back End_Test_name
WFD	Descriptive Workflows
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The reference documents listed in the table below cover the **applicable documentation** for the entire development and design process.

Title
H2IOSC MarketPlace Relazione SAL maggio 2025
Linee guida per la compilazione degli Items del MarketPlace H2IOSC
H2IOSC MarketPlace Providing Guide
Capitolato tecnico. PROGETTAZIONE E SVILUPPO DELLA PIATTAFORMA PER OSPITARE IL MARKETPLACE NELL'AMBITO DEL PIANO NAZIONALE RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) MISSIONE 4, "ISTRUZIONE E RICERCA" COMPONENTE 2, "DALLA RICERCA ALL'IMPRESA" INVESTIMENTO 3.1, "FONDO PER LA REALIZZAZIONE DI UN SISTEMA INTEGRATO DI INFRASTRUTTURE DI RICERCA E INNOVAZIONE" PROGETTO H2IOSC CUP B63C22000730005 CIG 9913670B47

Verification and Validation Process

TIME PLAN

The project's key milestones and their respective deadlines are shown in the following figure:

DESCRIPTION OF THE ENVIRONMENT AND TOOLS FOR VALIDATION AND VERIFICATION ACTIVITIES

The testing environment refers to a 'workbench development', a software development environment in which projects, applications or systems can be designed, tested and developed.

Verification control activity

The verification control activity is supported by the MarketPlace requirements database and the scenarios identified in the MarketPlace design document MKT_CNR_2024.07.05-REQUISITI_FUNZIONALI-V.02.0.

Each test procedure includes:

- Identification number;
- Name;
- Description;
- A detailed description of the technology environment and the hardware and software resources required to execute the test cases;
- The objective of the test;
- The reference is to the tested requirements.

The test plan⁹ also defines how anomalies will be handled, consistent with standard troubleshooting procedures.

This document was intended to serve as a guide during the testing phase, ensuring that each functionality is adequately tested and complies with the requirements (see Chapter 8 of MKT_CNR_2024.07.07-DOCUMENT_PROJECT_DOCUMENT).

⁹ The numbering of test cases has been deliberately structured in a non-sequential manner so that the inclusion of new tests can be facilitated in the future, if deemed useful, thanks to their modular integration, without the existing numbering and therefore the overall structure having to be modified and/or reorganised.

PASS/FAIL CRITERIA

In general, a test is considered to have been passed if the results match the expected ones, the exchange interfaces conform to the applicable documents, no error messages are generated during execution (in log files, dialogue boxes, etc.), and, if applicable, the database is updated correctly. A pass/fail criterion can be adopted for each test case according to the following table.

Test Case Status	Evaluation Criteria
Passed	The test case was successfully executed.
Passed with problems	The test case was executed, but at least one step was not satisfied. A solution can be found to complete the test case. The problem should be recorded in the Test Report and plotted as a Software Problem Report.
Failed	The test case was executed, but at least one pass-fail criterion was not met. The identified problem is blocking and a solution cannot be found. The problem should be recorded in the Test Report.

List of tests included in the current plan

The following section provides a description of the tests in order to plan the project's validation activity.

Back Office Test Plan

The Back Office is the operating environment reserved for administrators, curators and editors. It provides a dedicated interface for the controlled and traceable management of the platform's main activities: content ingestion (*harvesting*), validation and publication (*providing*), metadata management, and service configuration.

FT_BO_AAI Management

Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) is a system that manages user identities and access rights to resources.

Authentication verifies a user's identity through login with a username/password, defined after registration.

Authorization determines which resources a user can access and which actions they can perform. It defines the permissions and access levels granted to a user, depending on their identity and role.

TC_BO_001_ Admin Management

ID Function	FT_BO_AAI Management
Description	<p>The test verifies the Single Sign-On authentication service via Nanotec, allowing integrated access for institutional users.</p> <p>When users log in for the first time, the system automatically retrieves their data: email, name, access privileges (assigned in the back office), and consent to the terms of service.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Simplified and secure access for institutional users.- Alignment with federated authentication standards.- Centralised management of access rights based on role.
Actors	Admin

TC_BO_002_Roles management

ID Function	FT_BO_AAI Management
Description	<p>The test verifies the creation and management of custom roles in line with the platform's governance rules, which are based on different user types, and improves the security and operational consistency of the system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Creation, modification and deletion of custom roles.- Control of access levels and authorizations, according to policies defined at governance level.- Viewing and managing existing roles.
Actors	Admin

FT_BO Source management

TC_BO_005_Source management

ID Function	TC_BO_Source management
Description	The test verifies CRUD operations on provider records in order to manage the data sources authorised to provide metadata. In addition, the test verifies CRUD operations on the data sources to be harvested, in order to ensure that the sources are always up to date and appropriate for the platform's needs.
Actors	Admin

TC_BO_006_Infrastructure synergies

ID Function	TC_BO_Source management
Description	The test verifies the complementarity between RIs in the data management context.
Actors	Admin

FT_BO Harvesting

TC_BO_007 Harvesting console

ID Function	FT_BO_Harvesting
Description	The test verifies that the list of providers is displayed with search, filter, and sorting options, as well as quick access to the functions for viewing, creating, modifying, and deleting providers. Additionally, the test verifies the display of the list of jobs with search, filter, and sorting options, as well as the display of the reference provider, scheduling date, status (scheduled, completed, etc.), modification, duplication, and deletion of the job.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor

FT_BO_Items

TC_BO_009 Viewing Items

ID Function	FT_BO_Items
Description	The test verifies the exploration of MarketPlace items, divided into classes such as Datasets and Tools. The test highlights: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the page listing harvested items; - the page displaying information about harvested items; - editable information about harvested items.
Actors	Admin, Contributor, Curator

FT_BO_Workflow

TC_BO_010 Workflow

ID Function	FT_BO_Workflow
Description	The test verifies the workflow configuration in order to structure new solutions or data processing pipelines. Furthermore, the test verifies that the workflow is saved with a unique URI (Uniform Resource Identifier), which is generated via a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), and made available on the MarketPlace.
Actors	Contributor

FT_BO_Pilot

TC_BO_011 Pilot

ID Function	FT_BO_Pilot
Description	The test verifies the Pilot services implementation in order to structure new solutions or data processing pipelines.
Actors	Contributor

Front End Test Plan

The Front End is the public interface of the MarketPlace and is designed to enable end users to consult, search for, filter and share published resources. Developed using a mobile-first approach, the user interface focuses on accessibility, clarity and immediacy of the user experience. This allows for smooth, customisable navigation based on the user's profile and the type of available contents.

From the MarketPlace homepage, the user can log in and then search for and access the resources harvested through various user flows and related features.

FT_FE Homepage management

TC_FE_025 Homepage's presentation

ID Function

FT_FE_Homepage management

Scenario Description

The test verifies the Homepage's functionality and the resources that have been browsed.

Actors

Admin, Contributor, Curator, Subscriber

TC_FE_026 Mobile visualization

ID Function	FT_FE_Homepage management
Scenario Description	The test verifies that the resources are navigable from the homepage of the mobile phone.
Actors	Admin, Contributor, Curator, Subscriber

FT_FE Profile Management

TC_FE_030 New user registration

ID Function	FT_FE_Profile Management
Scenario Description	The test verifies that user registration on the MarketPlace platform is correctly managed.
Actors	Admin, Contributor, Curator

TC_FE_031 Login

ID Function	FT_FE_Profile management
Scenario Description	The test allows you to verify the login function in both nominal and non-nominal cases. The test phases include <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - access with correct credentials - access with incorrect credentials - appropriate error messages - handling edge cases (e.g., empty fields, invalid formats).
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

FT_FE Category Management

TC_FE_032 Select Category

ID Function	FT_FE_Category Management
Scenario Description	The test aims to verify that a catalogued resource, which may belong to different categories such as software tools, datasets, publications, projects and services, is present and selectable.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

TC_FE_033 Category tab management

ID Function	FT_FE_Category Management
Scenario Description	The test aims to verify that a catalogued resource, which may belong to different categories, such as software tools, datasets, publications, projects and services, is correctly managed.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

TC_FE_034 Saved Searches management

ID Function	FT_FE_Category Management
Scenario Description	The test aims to verify that a resource can be saved, modified, and deleted. It also verifies that searches performed on the platform can be recalled in order to quickly access results of interest, eliminating the need to manually repeat the same queries.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

FT_FE Search and resource display management

TC_FE_035 display of harvested resources

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Scenario Description	<p>From the MarketPlace homepage, you can search for and access harvested resources through various user flows and related features.</p> <p>The test verifies that the results of a MarketPlace search are displayed correctly, so you can easily identify and access the details of resources of interest.</p> <p>For each result, you can view the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- name- brief description- type (open access/permission request)- publication date- the number of views- relevant metadata to facilitate identification. <p>You can also view quick actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- View details- Save to favourites- Share- Cite. <p>The results are displayed in order of relevance to the search performed. If no results are found, you will receive a message inviting you to reformulate your search.</p>
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber Registered User/Viewer

TC_FE_036 search resources

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Scenario Description	<p>The test verifies the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Navigation of the resources available in the MarketPlace: that each resource has a unique URL that can be accessed via a browser.- The search engine's ability to find specific resources in the MarketPlace, explore results using advanced filtering options and navigate.- The feasibility of performing a simple search by entering a text string into the MarketPlace search bar to quickly find the most relevant resources available. As you type, the system suggests relevant keywords.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

TC_FE_037 filtering action

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Scenario Description	<p>The test verifies the functionality of the filters which enable users to refine their results based on various criteria.</p> <p>These filters include categories such as activity, keywords, sources, languages, document type, access type, and publication date.</p> <p>Results will be displayed in order of relevance to the initial search and selected filters.</p>
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

TC_FE_038 saving searches

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Scenario Description	The test verifies the ability to save, edit, and recall searches you have performed on the platform so that you can quickly access the results you are interested in without having to manually repeat the same queries. You can also delete any saved searches that are no longer useful.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

TC_FE_039 descriptive workflow

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Description	The test verifies the management of descriptive workflows, which allow you to describe an activity that can aggregate services and resources made available in the MarketPlace via a graphical interface. In particular, the test covers: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Adding steps to the WFD;- Adding steps that refer to services and datasets available in the WFD;- Uploading descriptive media (images, audio, or video) to associate with the WFD description;- Saving the WFD while checking the syntactic correctness of the published data;- Publishing the WFD by generating a URI.
Actors	Contributor

TC_FE_040 Citation Management

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Description	<p>The test verifies the possibility of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - copying a resource citation directly from the detail sheet, in order to use it in different formats (APA, MLA, Chicago, Harvard, IEEE, Vancouver, AMA); - exporting to bibliographic management software such as EndNote, Mendeley, Zotero, RefWorks, and BibTeX; - creating and saving thematic or project bibliographies; - sharing citations via email or social media.
Actors	Contributor

TC_FE_041 Access Public Resources

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Description	<p>The test verifies the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the display of item detail sheets, which allow users to consult detailed information, metadata, descriptions, multimedia content, and external links depending on their privileges; - free access to and consultation of public resources; - the ability to access the resource via a link to the unique URL (from an item's card) and view all the item's information: type (service/workflow), access (open access/permission required), title, description, CTA with link to the resource's unique URL, media (if present); - viewing the workflow steps; - viewing a series of details: contributor, curator, reviewer, contact, licence, activities, keywords, sources, field, languages; - viewing possible actions: Save to favourites, Share, Cite.
Actors	Contributor

TC_FE_042 Bookmark Management

ID Function	FT_FE_Search and resource display management
Description	<p>The test checks the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - saving and organising resources as favourites in your personal profile; - organising favourites into folders/categories and removing those that are no longer considered useful.
Actors	Contributor

FT FE User Interface

TC_FE_043 UI management

ID Function	FT_FE_ User Interface
Scenario Description	<p>The test verifies the correct functioning of the user interface and consistency between the front end and the back office regarding:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear, goal-oriented navigation; - Search functionality, filters and results display; - Consistency between desktop and mobile displays.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber

Back End Test Plan

The Back End represents the application core of the system and implements all MarketPlace logic. Its main features, including item management, harvesting and providing flows, indexing and publishing, are accessible via a set of REST APIs from both the back office and the front end. This architectural choice allows for high modularity and enables integration with other external systems in a federated manner.

FT_BE_CRUD

TC_BE_060 CRUD Operation management

ID Function	FT_BE_CRUD
Description	The test verifies that the necessary logic and services for managing fundamental data operations have been implemented: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create (creation), - Read (reading), - Update (updating), - Delete (deletion).
Actors	Contributor

FT_BE_profile management

TC_BE_061 role management

ID Function	FT_BE_Profile management
Description	The test verifies that roles have been assigned correctly to ensure the correct functioning of the related back office features, such as the creation, modification and deletion of roles; the configuration of permissions; the display of roles in lists; and the search for roles.
Actors	Contributor

TC_BE_062 user management

ID Function	FT_BE_Profile management
Description	The test verifies user management to ensure the correct functioning of related back office features, such as the creation, modification and deletion of users; the assignment of roles and related infrastructure; the display of users in lists; the implementation of filters; and the user search.
Actors	Contributor

FT_BE dictionary management

TC_BE_063 dictionary management

ID Function	FT_BE_dictionary management
Description	The test verifies the correct management of dictionaries: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- updating a dictionary by importing external files (available in standard formats, in CSV according to a predefined model, or in SKOS);- viewing dictionaries, dictionary reports;- analysis of the content of ttl/SKOS vocabularies, and implementation of vocabulary parsing procedures.
Actors	Contributor

FT_BE Source management

TC_BE_064_Source management

ID Function	FT_BE_Source management
Description	The test verifies that services have been implemented to integrate and manage data sources, from which structured and semi-structured metadata is retrieved from the back office in order to update the repository.
Actors	Contributor

FT_BE Storage service

TC_BE_065 Storage service

ID Function	FT_BO_Workflow
Description	The test verifies the persistence of, and efficient access to, the main entities of the MarketPlace, using a write database (Write DB) and a read database (Read DB).
Actors	Contributor

FT_BE_API

TC_BE_065 API Implementation

ID Function	FT_BO_Workflow
Description	The test verifies the persistence and efficiency of the implemented APIs.
Actors	Contributor

Traceability Matrix: Requirements vs Test

ID-Req	REQ Description	TEST ID
REQ-001	The MarketPlace shall be an online tool to increase the visibility and enhancement of data sources, services, and resources provided by RIs and the broader research community.	TC_BO_005_Source management TC_BE_064_Source management
REQ-002	The MarketPlace shall be hosted within the national cloud infrastructure developed under the H2IOSC project.	Documentation
REQ-003	The implementation of the MarketPlace shall ensure full compliance with the FAIR principles.	
REQ-004	The MarketPlace shall contribute to developing synergies and complementarities in data management among the participating RIs.	TC_BO_006_Infrastructure synergies
REQ-005	The MarketPlace shall ensure integration and interoperability of data and tools within and around the H2IOSC national cloud infrastructure.	Documentation
REQ-006	The MarketPlace shall include a software platform to enhance the offerings of resource and service providers and offer end users a set of advanced search and interaction functionalities.	Documentation
REQ-007	The MarketPlace shall include a governance model and a stakeholder engagement system.	
REQ-008	A dedicated action will be implemented to populate the MarketPlace catalogue with resources from both Italian RIs and other national and corresponding European nodes: national RI registries will be aligned, and interoperability with the SSHOC and EOSC marketplaces will be ensured to connect the national and European dimensions in terms of visibility, availability, and community engagement.	TC_BO_004_dictionary management TC_BO_005_Source management TC_FE_035 display of harvested resources TC_FE_036 search resources

		TC_BE_063 dictionary management TC_BE_064_Source management
REQ-009	The H2IOSC MarketPlace will rely on resources evaluated based on their Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and approved for inclusion in the catalogue by participating RIs.	Documentation
REQ-010	Work Package 1 (WP1) is dedicated to the graphic design that will define the MarketPlace's visual identity.	Documentation
REQ-011	Work Package 2 (WP2) is dedicated to identifying user requirements and needs, selecting resources and tools to be included in the MarketPlace, and developing a classification system for the disciplinary domains related to H2IOSC.	Documentation
REQ-012	Work Package 3 (WP3) is dedicated to identifying resources to be included in the MarketPlace, including automatic import and the definition of data exchange procedures with existing and relevant European marketplaces and catalogues, including EOSC and SSHOC.	Documentation
REQ-013	Work Package 4 (WP4) will create the project's Common Semantic Framework. The data model and classification logic of the MarketPlace must be based on the results of this WP. Additionally, the cloud infrastructure hosting the MarketPlace will be developed here.	Documentation
REQ-014	Work Package 6 (WP6) will produce tools to be included as entries in the MarketPlace.	Documentation
REQ-015	Work Package 7 (WP7) implements a series of pilot projects to be included in the MarketPlace.	TC_BO_011 Pilot Documentation
REQ-016	The MarketPlace is a web platform providing a single access point to tools, datasets, services, and best practices from the participating research infrastructures.	TC_FE_030 New user registration TC_FE_031 Login
REQ-017	Researchers will be able to find, process, enrich, analyse, and compare research data, services, and tools beyond the boundaries of individual repositories or institutions.	TC_FE_032 Select Category
REQ-018	The MarketPlace must be an intuitive platform, a single point of access where scholars from various disciplines in the field of Social and Cultural Innovation (SCI) can find solutions and resources for their research. It will also serve as an online tool to increase visibility, enhancement, and accessibility of data sources, services, and resources developed by research infrastructures.	TC_FE_033 Category tab management
REQ-019	The MarketPlace will be aligned with the national and European catalogues of participating research infrastructures and with portals and catalogues of other European and national infrastructures, particularly EOSC and SSHOC.	TC_BO_006_Infrastructure synergies

REQ-020	Data and metadata will be formalised according to the vision of the Common Semantic Framework developed in WP4; full compliance with FAIR principles will also be ensured.	Documentation
REQ-021	The main functionality of the MarketPlace is the catalogue. Catalogue entries consist of descriptions of Tools and Aggregations. Tools are descriptions of physical or digital services, while aggregations are more complex services composed of multiple tools used together to meet specific research needs.	TC_FE_039 descriptive workflow
REQ-022	Tools used within an aggregation must be mentioned, and a link to their descriptions in the catalogue must be provided. Different aggregations may share the same tools.	TC_FE_039 descriptive workflow
REQ-023	It must also be possible to compare each tool or aggregation with other relevant entries in the catalogue, based on various criteria identified during the requirements analysis phase (e.g., similar tools/aggregations, alternative options to perform the same research task, additional offerings from the same service provider, etc.).	TC_FE_037 filtering action
REQ-024	By reading the descriptions, users will be able to choose catalogue entries (tools or aggregations) that best meet their current research needs.	TC_FE_039 descriptive workflow
REQ-025	The MarketPlace will be a complex platform, and users must be guided simply through navigation among different sections and services.	TP_FE_005 Select Category Documentation
REQ-026	Level 0 services are those offered by the MarketPlace but not listed in the catalogue. They are specific to the MarketPlace and aim to enrich the user experience. Examples of Level 0 services include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User-oriented features (navigation, personal and shareable "favourites" lists, personal workflows...) - Governance-oriented features (administration, decision-support services, measurements and evaluations, statistics...) 	TC_BO_010 Workflow TC_FE_041 Access Public Resources TC_FE_042 Bookmark Management
REQ-026-01	Advanced features (Level 0) Level 0 features are advanced features offered to registered MarketPlace users: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User services, including customisable and shareable lists of "favourites" and personal workflows. In the latter case, users must be able to select a combination of Level 1 tools to be used together and in sequence for their search through a workflow. The MarketPlace must return a configuration file to be provided as input to another H2IOSC implementation (i.e. outside the MarketPlace), which will enable the corresponding tasks to be executed in combination. 	TC_BO_010 Workflow TC_FE_025 Homepage's presentation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customised services for service providers, allowing them to independently describe the Level 1 tools (and possibly Level 2 aggregations) they offer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Recommendation services based on Artificial Intelligence o Advanced and interactive visualisations, with statistics on MarketPlace data and its level of usage. 	
REQ-027	<p>Level 1 Tools</p> <p>The description of the tools must include instructions on how to access and use them: for example, in the case of a digital service, the link to access it must be provided.</p> <p>Level 1 tools include digital services, such as software packages and datasets, as well as web platforms, along with physical tools offered by research infrastructure laboratories.</p> <p>External services acquired from third parties (e.g., through the automatic import of external catalogues, such as those from EOSC or SSHOC) will therefore be listed as Level 1 tools.</p>	Documentation
REQ-027-01	<p>Level 1 tools on the MarketPlace may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital services, such as access to complete web platforms, cloud services or ready-to-use APIs; - Physical services. Users can discover these and book a visit through the MarketPlace; - Datasets to download; - Software that can be purchased, downloaded, compiled or used directly; - Ontologies, controlled vocabularies and data models for re-use; - Training resources are also available, both digital and in-person. 	Documentation
REQ-028	<p>Level 2 includes the aggregations described above.</p> <p>Level 2 aggregations will typically consist of pilot projects, particularly those carried out under WP7, which make use of Level 1 tools.</p>	TC_BO_011 Pilot
REQ-028-01	<p>Level 2 aggregations include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - H2IOSC pilot projects to be developed in WP7. - Other possible pilots and complex services implemented by research infrastructures participating in H2IOSC. - Ready-to-use research workflows, i.e., “recipes” for performing specific research activities using a set of Level 1 tools. 	TC_BO_011 Pilot TC_BO_010 Workflow
REQ-029	<p>In the MarketPlace's implementation, some of the existing application services available to participating research infrastructures may be reused. These include the IDEM GARR AAI</p>	TC_BO_001_ Admin Management

	federated authentication system, which can be used to manage user registration and authentication in the MarketPlace.	TC_BO_002_Roles management TC_BO_003_User management TC_FE_001 New user registration TC_FE_002 Login
REQ-030	Some of the MarketPlace features will need to be generalised so that they can be used by other H2IOSC implementations, particularly by the WP7 pilot projects.	TC_BO_011 Pilot
REQ-031	The catalogue will be populated with Level 1 and Level 2 services, entered either manually by editors accessing a data entry back office, or automatically imported from the catalogues of participating research infrastructures and similar national and international initiatives.	TC_BO_004_dictionary management
REQ-032	The implementation of the MarketPlace must ensure interoperability with the catalogues of EOSC and other European infrastructures (including that of SSHOC). Interoperability must work in both directions: on the one hand, EOSC and SSHOC entries that are relevant and pertinent to the domain of Social and Cultural Innovation must populate the H2IOSC MarketPlace; on the other hand, H2IOSC Level 1 and 2 services must be able to be published in these catalogues. The logic behind these exchanges will be defined in the Project's Requirements Analysis phase: in any case, automatic and continuous exchanges in both directions must be guaranteed.	Documentation
REQ-033	The MarketPlace must provide APIs and endpoints to query and access its data through standard protocols.	TC_BE_065 API Implementation
REQ-034	The MarketPlace will have to provide data modeling, ensuring full compatibility with the Common Semantic Framework of WP4 and, in general, with standard ontologies and linked-data repositories. This is part of the general support for FAIR principles that the MarketPlace will have to guarantee in the management of its data.	Documentation
REQ-035	The MarketPlace will need to implement governance features, including ad hoc dashboards with statistics, reporting systems, and business intelligence.	TC_FE_025 Homepage's presentation
REQ-036	The MarketPlace must provide a help desk system with ticketing functionality and a workflow to manage user requests.	TC_BO_010 Workflow
REQ-037	User Research. Through User Experience (UX) research, the expectations of target users and their main problems they expect to solve via the MarketPlace will be better identified.	Documentation
REQ-038	The graphic design produced in WP1 must be properly adapted to the platform to create an intuitive, visually appealing user	TC_FE_025 Homepage's presentation

	interface. Tools such as wireframing, prototyping, and iterative feedback cycles will be used in this phase to ensure an optimal user experience.	
REQ-039	It must be ensured that the MarketPlace's user interface adapts optimally to mobile devices, providing a smooth and intuitive experience.	TC_FE_026 Mobile visualization
REQ-040	The definitions of MarketPlace functionalities and types of catalogue entries (Level 1 and Level 2), including the dynamics for their population (manual and automatic), must be clearly specified.	Documentation
REQ-041	Describe the design of the software architecture, with its different components and their relationships and interactions, to support the desired functionalities.	Documentation
REQ-042	Describe the detailed execution plan, a complete project roadmap for the contracting authority to approve.	Documentation
REQ-043	The platform must be secure, scalable, and user-oriented.	TC_FE_025 Homepage's presentation TC_BE_064_Source management
REQ-044	The work must be carried out using an AGILE methodology, providing H2IOSC stakeholders with full visibility of, and access to, the software repositories and the project management platform chosen by the awarded company for executing the project.	Documentation
REQ-045	Development must be carried out through iterations producing incremental releases: the awarded company must provide a staging environment in their server farm, where the various MarketPlace releases can be installed and reviewed by H2IOSC stakeholders.	Documentation
REQ-046	Where possible, all software developed in the course of the project must be released as open source. Furthermore, when possible, software products used for implementation should preferably be open source, or at least licence-free, for the contracting authority, both presently and in the future.	Documentation
REQ-047	Implementation of the automatic import component is required to populate the MarketPlace catalogue via harvesting from selected external catalogues, using their APIs, and — where not possible otherwise — via web-scraping techniques.	TC_BE_065 API Implementation
REQ-048	Back end development: Create the server side infrastructure and services to implement the MarketPlace's business logic. This includes designing and implementing databases, APIs, security measures, and integration with external systems. The development team must ensure scalability, performance, and robustness to handle high volumes of user requests.	Documentation

REQ-049	<p>Front end development:</p> <p>Front end developers must translate the UX/UI design into functional web and mobile interfaces. Use of modern interactive front end frameworks such as Angular or React is required, with development in TypeScript. The team should also prioritise performance optimisation and compatibility across various desktop and mobile browsers. Regarding localisation, the MarketPlace UI must support both Italian and English content.</p>	Documentation
REQ-050	<p>Testing and Quality Assurance:</p> <p>Throughout the software development phase, rigorous testing processes must be conducted using various methodologies, including unit and integration testing, performance and security testing, and final acceptance testing, with a plan approved by H2IOSC stakeholders.</p>	Documentation
REQ-051	<p>Production installation and go live:</p> <p>Once development and testing are complete, the MarketPlace will be ready for production deployment on the H2IOSC cloud infrastructure. The launch phase must include a carefully planned release strategy, ensuring a smooth transition from development to actual go live.</p>	Documentation
REQ-052	Initial data population service must be provided through automatic harvesting and batch import from existing catalogues.	TC_BO_007 Harvesting console
REQ-053	Training materials must be provided on how to use the MarketPlace back-office functionalities, including data entry services, the help-desk management system, the governance dashboard, and all other functionalities supporting platform monitoring and control.	Documentation
REQ-054	Post-launch support and maintenance must be provided, covering performance monitoring, routine maintenance, handling user feedback (second-level help desk), technical support, bug fixes, and security patch installation. Extending this activity beyond the end of the H2IOSC project will be evaluated as added value in the offer.	Documentation
REQ-055	Evolutionary maintenance of the software must be provided, enabling extension of the software through modifications, improvements, and new functionalities after release. The number of days the designated party will guarantee for this activity post go live will be evaluated as added value in the offer.	Documentation
REQ-056	The warranty provided by the contractor must cover a period of 6 (six) months from the date of passing the service compliance check, unless a better offer is presented during the tender. This warranty must include all activities needed to maintain system functionality. It also covers any travel expenses and possible	Documentation

	labour costs at the contracting authority. During the warranty period, the contractor must commit to providing free upgrades to software licences.	
REQ-057	<p>Software ownership:</p> <p>All software developed by the contractor under the contract shall remain the property of the contracting authority, which may reuse the software upon contract expiration. To this end, the contractor must deliver a complete system backup, all updated source code, and full documentation according to international standards, as well as detailed user and system administrator manuals, 30 days before contract expiration or termination.</p>	Documentation
REQ-058	<p>Technical assistance, support, and maintenance:</p> <p>In case of malfunction, the contractor must be able to respond promptly to a report sent via certified email (PEC) within a maximum of 5 (five) working days. This intervention is aimed at immediate assistance and system functionality restoration or, if not possible, the evaluation of necessary corrective actions.</p>	Documentation
REQ-059	<p>Execution modalities:</p> <p>The service will generally be carried out remotely. Monthly on site meetings at the contracting authority premises are planned. The frequency of meetings may be adjusted based on project progress.</p> <p>The contractor's Project Manager must always attend these meetings, alongside the Contract Execution Director. Each meeting will result in official meeting minutes, which will be distributed to both the contracting authority's and contractor's project teams.</p>	Documentation
REQ-060	Execution timeframe	Documentation

Traceability Matrix: Requirements vs Development Issues

The following table is a work in progress as it is being completed until the end of the H2IOSC project.

ID-Req	REQ Description	Issue ID
REQ-001	The MarketPlace shall be an online tool to increase the visibility and enhancement of data sources, services, and resources provided by RIs and the broader research community.	#19

REQ-002	The MarketPlace shall be hosted within the national cloud infrastructure developed under the H2IOSC project.	
REQ-003	The implementation of the MarketPlace shall ensure full compliance with the FAIR principles.	
REQ-004	The MarketPlace shall contribute to developing synergies and complementarities in data management among the participating RIs.	
REQ-005	The MarketPlace shall ensure integration and interoperability of data and tools within and around the H2IOSC national cloud infrastructure.	
REQ-006	The MarketPlace shall include a software platform to enhance the offerings of resource and service providers and offer end users a set of advanced search and interaction functionalities.	#17 #100
REQ-007	The MarketPlace shall include a governance model and a stakeholder engagement system.	
REQ-008	A dedicated action will be implemented to populate the MarketPlace catalogue with resources from both Italian RIs and other national and corresponding European nodes: national RI registries will be aligned, and interoperability with the SSHOC and EOSC marketplaces will be ensured to connect the national and European dimensions in terms of visibility, availability, and community engagement.	#137
REQ-009	The H2IOSC MarketPlace will rely on resources evaluated based on their Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and approved for inclusion in the catalogue by participating RIs.	
REQ-010	Work Package 1 (WP1) is dedicated to the graphic design that will define the MarketPlace's visual identity.	
REQ-011	Work Package 2 (WP2) is dedicated to identifying user requirements and needs, selecting resources and tools to be included in the MarketPlace, and developing a classification system for the disciplinary domains related to H2IOSC.	
REQ-012	Work Package 3 (WP3) is dedicated to identifying resources to be included in the MarketPlace, including automatic import and the definition of data exchange procedures with existing and relevant European marketplaces and catalogues, including EOSC and SSHOC.	
REQ-013	Work Package 4 (WP4) will create the project's Common Semantic Framework. The data model and classification logic of the MarketPlace must be based on the results of this WP. Additionally, the cloud infrastructure hosting the MarketPlace will be developed here.	
REQ-014	Work Package 6 (WP6) will produce tools to be included as entries in the MarketPlace.	

REQ-015	Work Package 7 (WP7) implements a series of pilot projects to be included in the MarketPlace.	
REQ-016	The MarketPlace is a web platform providing a single access point to tools, datasets, services, and best practices from the participating research infrastructures.	104
REQ-017	Researchers will be able to find, process, enrich, analyse, and compare research data, services, and tools beyond the boundaries of individual repositories or institutions.	#99
REQ-018	The MarketPlace must be an intuitive platform, a single point of access where scholars from various disciplines in the field of Social and Cultural Innovation (SCI) can find solutions and resources for their research. It will also serve as an online tool to increase visibility, enhancement, and accessibility of data sources, services, and resources developed by research infrastructures.	#19
REQ-019	The MarketPlace will be aligned with the national and European catalogues of participating research infrastructures and with portals and catalogues of other European and national infrastructures, particularly EOSC and SSHOC.	OAI-PMH
REQ-020	Data and metadata will be formalised according to the vision of the Common Semantic Framework developed in WP4; full compliance with FAIR principles will also be ensured.	
REQ-021	The main functionality of the MarketPlace is the catalogue. Catalogue entries consist of descriptions of Tools and Aggregations. Tools are descriptions of physical or digital services, while aggregations are more complex services composed of multiple tools used together to meet specific research needs.	105
REQ-022	Tools used within an aggregation must be mentioned, and a link to their descriptions in the catalogue must be provided. Different aggregations may share the same tools.	
REQ-023	It must also be possible to compare each tool or aggregation with other relevant entries in the catalogue, based on various criteria identified during the requirements analysis phase (e.g., similar tools/aggregations, alternative options to perform the same research task, additional offerings from the same service provider, etc.).	
REQ-024	By reading the descriptions, users will be able to choose catalogue entries (tools or aggregations) that best meet their current research needs.	
REQ-025	The MarketPlace will be a complex platform, and users must be guided simply through navigation among different sections and services.	#17; #120 103

REQ-026	<p>Level 0 services are those offered by the MarketPlace but not listed in the catalogue. They are specific to the MarketPlace and aim to enrich the user experience. Examples of Level 0 services include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User-oriented features (navigation, personal and shareable "favourites" lists, personal workflows...) - Governance-oriented features (administration, decision-support services, measurements and evaluations, statistics...) 	#17; #120; #123; #125; #126; #127 #100 103 106 107 108
REQ-026-01	<p>Advanced features (Level 0)</p> <p>Level 0 features are advanced features offered to registered MarketPlace users:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User services, including customisable and shareable lists of "favourites" and personal workflows. In the latter case, users must be able to select a combination of Level 1 tools to be used together and in sequence for their search through a workflow. The MarketPlace must return a configuration file to be provided as input to another H2IOSC implementation (i.e. outside the MarketPlace), which will enable the corresponding tasks to be executed in combination. - Customised services for service providers, allowing them to independently describe the Level 1 tools (and possibly Level 2 aggregations) they offer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Recommendation services based on Artificial Intelligence o Advanced and interactive visualisations, with statistics on MarketPlace data and its level of usage. 	#123; #124; #130; #131; #132; #133; #134; #135; #136; #137; 102 103
REQ-027	<p>Level 1 Tools</p> <p>The description of the tools must include instructions on how to access and use them: for example, in the case of a digital service, the link to access it must be provided.</p> <p>Level 1 tools include digital services, such as software packages and datasets, as well as web platforms, along with physical tools offered by research infrastructure laboratories.</p> <p>External services acquired from third parties (e.g., through the automatic import of external catalogues, such as those from EOSC or SSHOC) will therefore be listed as Level 1 tools.</p>	
REQ-027-01	<p>Level 1 tools on the MarketPlace may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital services, such as access to complete web platforms, cloud services or ready-to-use APIs; - Physical services. Users can discover these and book a visit through the MarketPlace; - Datasets to download; 	#124; 128; #129

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Software that can be purchased, downloaded, compiled or used directly; - Ontologies, controlled vocabularies and data models for re-use; - Training resources are also available, both digital and in-person. 	
REQ-028	<p>Level 2 includes the aggregations described above.</p> <p>Level 2 aggregations will typically consist of pilot projects, particularly those carried out under WP7, which make use of Level 1 tools.</p>	
REQ-028-01	<p>Level 2 aggregations include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - H2IOSC pilot projects to be developed in WP7. - Other possible pilots and complex services implemented by research infrastructures participating in H2IOSC. - Ready-to-use research workflows, i.e., “recipes” for performing specific research activities using a set of Level 1 tools. 	
REQ-029	<p>In the MarketPlace's implementation, some of the existing application services available to participating research infrastructures may be reused. These include the IDEM GARR AAI federated authentication system, which can be used to manage user registration and authentication in the MarketPlace.</p>	#12; #17
REQ-030	<p>Some of the MarketPlace features will need to be generalised so that they can be used by other H2IOSC implementations, particularly by the WP7 pilot projects.</p>	
REQ-031	<p>The catalogue will be populated with Level 1 and Level 2 services, entered either manually by editors accessing a data entry back office, or automatically imported from the catalogues of participating research infrastructures and similar national and international initiatives.</p>	#12; #17
REQ-032	<p>The implementation of the MarketPlace must ensure interoperability with the catalogues of EOSC and other European infrastructures (including that of SSHOC). Interoperability must work in both directions: on the one hand, EOSC and SSHOC entries that are relevant and pertinent to the domain of Social and Cultural Innovation must populate the H2IOSC MarketPlace; on the other hand, H2IOSC Level 1 and 2 services must be able to be published in these catalogues. The logic behind these exchanges will be defined in the Project's Requirements Analysis phase: in any case, automatic and continuous exchanges in both directions must be guaranteed.</p>	#137
REQ-033	<p>The MarketPlace must provide APIs and endpoints to query and access its data through standard protocols.</p>	

REQ-034	The MarketPlace will have to provide data modeling, ensuring full compatibility with the Common Semantic Framework of WP4 and, in general, with standard ontologies and linked-data repositories. This is part of the general support for FAIR principles that the MarketPlace will have to guarantee in the management of its data.	
REQ-035	The MarketPlace will need to implement governance features, including ad hoc dashboards with statistics, reporting systems, and business intelligence.	
REQ-036	The MarketPlace must provide a help desk system with ticketing functionality and a workflow to manage user requests.	
REQ-037	User Research. Through User Experience (UX) research, the expectations of target users and their main problems they expect to solve via the MarketPlace will be better identified.	99 100 102 103
REQ-038	The graphic design produced in WP1 must be properly adapted to the platform to create an intuitive, visually appealing user interface. Tools such as wireframing, prototyping, and iterative feedback cycles will be used in this phase to ensure an optimal user experience.	
REQ-039	It must be ensured that the MarketPlace's user interface adapts optimally to mobile devices, providing a smooth and intuitive experience.	102
REQ-040	The definitions of MarketPlace functionalities and types of catalogue entries (Level 1 and Level 2), including the dynamics for their population (manual and automatic), must be clearly specified.	
REQ-041	Describe the design of the software architecture, with its different components and their relationships and interactions, to support the desired functionalities.	
REQ-042	Describe the detailed execution plan, a complete project roadmap for the contracting authority to approve.	
REQ-043	The platform must be secure, scalable, and user-oriented.	
REQ-044	The work must be carried out using an AGILE methodology, providing H2IOSC stakeholders with full visibility of, and access to, the software repositories and the project management platform chosen by the awarded company for executing the project.	OFFERTA ECONOMICA
REQ-045	Development must be carried out through iterations producing incremental releases: the awarded company must provide a staging environment in their server farm, where the various MarketPlace releases can be installed and reviewed by H2IOSC stakeholders.	

REQ-046	Where possible, all software developed in the course of the project must be released as open source. Furthermore, when possible, software products used for implementation should preferably be open source, or at least licence-free, for the contracting authority, both presently and in the future.	
REQ-047	Implementation of the automatic import component is required to populate the MarketPlace catalogue via harvesting from selected external catalogues, using their APIs, and — where not possible otherwise — via web-scraping techniques.	#122
REQ-048	Back end development: Create the server side infrastructure and services to implement the MarketPlace’s business logic. This includes designing and implementing databases, APIs, security measures, and integration with external systems. The development team must ensure scalability, performance, and robustness to handle high volumes of user requests.	#42; #121
REQ-049	Front end development: Front end developers must translate the UX/UI design into functional web and mobile interfaces. Use of modern interactive front end frameworks such as Angular or React is required, with development in TypeScript. The team should also prioritise performance optimisation and compatibility across various desktop and mobile browsers. Regarding localisation, the MarketPlace UI must support both Italian and English content.	#138; #139
REQ-050	Testing and Quality Assurance: Throughout the software development phase, rigorous testing processes must be conducted using various methodologies, including unit and integration testing, performance and security testing, and final acceptance testing, with a plan approved by H2IOSC stakeholders.	
REQ-051	Production installation and go live: Once development and testing are complete, the MarketPlace will be ready for production deployment on the H2IOSC cloud infrastructure. The launch phase must include a carefully planned release strategy, ensuring a smooth transition from development to actual go live.	
REQ-052	Initial data population service must be provided through automatic harvesting and batch import from existing catalogues.	#122
REQ-053	Training materials must be provided on how to use the MarketPlace back-office functionalities, including data entry services, the help-desk management system, the governance dashboard, and all other functionalities supporting platform monitoring and control.	

REQ-054	Post-launch support and maintenance must be provided, covering performance monitoring, routine maintenance, handling user feedback (second-level help desk), technical support, bug fixes, and security patch installation. Extending this activity beyond the end of the H2IOSC project will be evaluated as added value in the offer.	
REQ-055	Evolutionary maintenance of the software must be provided, enabling extension of the software through modifications, improvements, and new functionalities after release. The number of days the designated party will guarantee for this activity post go live will be evaluated as added value in the offer.	
REQ-056	The warranty provided by the contractor must cover a period of 6 (six) months from the date of passing the service compliance check, unless a better offer is presented during the tender. This warranty must include all activities needed to maintain system functionality. It also covers any travel expenses and possible labour costs at the contracting authority. During the warranty period, the contractor must commit to providing free upgrades to software licences.	
REQ-057	Software ownership: All software developed by the contractor under the contract shall remain the property of the contracting authority, which may reuse the software upon contract expiration. To this end, the contractor must deliver a complete system backup, all updated source code, and full documentation according to international standards, as well as detailed user and system administrator manuals, 30 days before contract expiration or termination.	
REQ-058	Technical assistance, support, and maintenance: In case of malfunction, the contractor must be able to respond promptly to a report sent via certified email (PEC) within a maximum of 5 (five) working days. This intervention is aimed at immediate assistance and system functionality restoration or, if not possible, the evaluation of necessary corrective actions.	
REQ-059	Execution modalities: The service will generally be carried out remotely. Monthly on site meetings at the contracting authority premises are planned. The frequency of meetings may be adjusted based on project progress. The contractor's Project Manager must always attend these meetings, alongside the Contract Execution Director. Each meeting will result in official meeting minutes, which will be	

	distributed to both the contracting authority's and contractor's project teams.	
REQ-060	Execution timeframe	

Acceptance Matrix

The test plan and procedures document provide a report on the results of executing the integration and verification testing procedures.

The test documents generated during the testing activities track the entire validation procedure and are ultimately used for system qualification and acceptance by the developer.

Test ID	Test Result	Note	Date

The above table will be evaluated at the end of the system testing and validation phase.

Appendix

This section provides **two examples of test procedures** that must be performed to validate the system.

TEST PROCEDURES

For example, two test procedures that will be performed are shown below.

TP_FE_002 Login

ID Function	FT_FE_Profile management
Scenario Description	<p>The test allows you to verify the login function in nominal and non-nominal cases. The test phases include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - access with correct credentials; - access with incorrect credentials; - appropriate error messages. <p>Handling edge cases (e.g., empty fields, invalid formats).</p>
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber
Requirement Ref	
<p><u>Step:</u> Login using the correct credentials</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open the login page. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Enter a valid username/email address. 3. Enter the correct password. 4. Click 'Login' or press 'Enter'. 	<p><u>Expected result:</u> The user is redirected either to the dashboard or to the homepage.</p>

TP_FE_005 Select Category

ID Function	FT_FE_Category Management
Scenario Description	The test aims to verify that a catalogued resource which can belong to different categories, such as software tools, datasets, publications, projects and services, is present and selectable.
Actors	Admin, Curator, Contributor, Subscriber
Requirement Ref	
<p><u>Step:</u> After logging in using the user credentials</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Select 'Tool' category and start the search <p>No results are shown.</p>	

7.4 ANNEX 4

THE FINAL VERSION OF THE SYSTEM OF DASHBOARDS: H2IOSC MARKETPLACE - STATISTICS DASHBOARD

Annex 4¹⁰ illustrates the **integrated dashboard**, which is accessible from the back office and ensures **constant monitoring of activities** carried out within the H2IOSC MarketPlace. In line with transparency, it offers a unified and interactive view on two key areas by combining publication and interaction data:

- **Assets** (sources/items) published in the MarketPlace
- MarketPlace **user interactions**.

This dashboard system optimises **decision-making**, by grounding it in measurable data and making the process faster and more effective. It also significantly improves **operational efficiency** and the **end-user experience**.

MarketPlace statistics

To ensure constant monitoring of the progress of activities carried out in the MarketPlace and improve the team's decision-making capacity based on measurable data, a Dashboard is proposed. It is accessible from the back office and displays a series of statistics that can be filtered according to certain parameters and updated in real time.

The goal is to offer a unified and interactive view on two fundamental areas:

- Assets (sources/items) published in the MarketPlace
- MarketPlace user interactions.

Statistics dashboard design and UX

The MarketPlace Statistics Dashboard has been designed using a data-driven, mobile-first approach to provide a fast, intuitive, professional experience that makes interpreting data quick and easy, ensuring:

- **Clarity and immediacy** - with interactive charts, at-a-glance indicators and quick filters by period, type and supplier;
- **Consistent navigation** - a modular layout and visual hierarchy guide the user from general KPIs to analytical detail without causing cognitive overload;
- **Flexibility** - customisable panels based on the user's role, showing only relevant metrics.

General summary, e.g.

- Total number of publications (items) present in the MarketPlace
- Total number of publications (items) harvested in the MarketPlace
- Total number of registered MarketPlace users
- Total number of errors detected during harvesting.

¹⁰ The screenshots shown in this Annex, extracted from the technical documentation provided by the M.E.T.A. company, are from the MarketPlace development environment (DEV) and are for demonstration purposes only. The data in the charts is illustrative only and does not represent any real or official MarketPlace information.

Statistics on resources (items) published in the MarketPlace

The user enabled to log into and access the MarketPlace back office enters the Statistics Dashboard section to view and analyse data on published resources (items), in order to monitor activities carried out within the platform.

Data displayed

- Total publications (items) present in the MarketPlace divided by infrastructure;
- Total publications (items) harvested in the MarketPlace divided by infrastructure;
- Total publications (items) present in the MarketPlace divided by type;
- Total publications (items) harvested in the MarketPlace divided by type;
- Publications (items) present in the MarketPlace distributed over time;
- Publications (items) harvested in the MarketPlace distributed over time;
- Time trend of publications (items) present in the MarketPlace and comparison between types;
- Time trend of publications (items) harvested in the MarketPlace and comparison between types.

Available filters

- Infrastructure: all infrastructures or individual infrastructure;
- Time Frame: this month, last 3 months, this year, all.

Advantages

- Immediate feedback on the trend of the most active publications and suppliers;
- Rapid identification of errors and technical criticalities;
- Possibility of planning targeted interventions and corrective actions.

MarketPlace user interaction statistics

The user enabled to log into and access the MarketPlace back office enters the Statistics Dashboard section to view and analyse data on user interactions with the platform, in order to monitor the activities carried out and improve support.

Data displayed

- Total number of users present in the MarketPlace distributed over time;
- Total number of bookmarks saved by users distributed over time;
- Total number of searches saved by users over time;
- Time trend of bookmarks saved by users and comparison between types;
- Top 10 publications (items) viewed most by users.

Available filters

- Infrastructure: all infrastructures or individual infrastructure;
- Time Period: this month, last 3 months, this year, all.

Advantages

- Clear view of community growth and usage preferences;
- Ability to customise services and communications based on user habits;
- Support for development and marketing decisions thanks to real-time metrics.

Conclusions

The MarketPlace Statistics Dashboard provides a comprehensive and integrated overview of activities carried out within the platform by combining publication and interaction data. The main expected benefits are:

- Greater **transparency** for platform managers;
- Faster, **data-driven strategic decision-making**;
- Improved **operational efficiency** and **end-user experience**.

7.5 ANNEX 5

THE FINAL VERSION OF THE RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM BASED ON AI

The **recommendation system** adopted by the MarketPlace is derived from that developed for **the E-RIHS services catalogue**.

The **E-RIHS service catalogue** has been developed on a robust and modular system architecture, designed to ensure independence and interoperability with external services, such as ORCID, and to comply with EOSC specifications. The platform integrates an intuitive user interface that guides users in selecting services, supported by a high-performance back end based on *Elasticsearch*, capable of performing fast and accurate searches.

The user experience was designed with the needs of the scientific community in mind, with the aim of making the search engine accessible even to non-expert users. In this initial phase, as a sufficiently large dataset for training AI models is not yet available, the team has started collecting data through a pilot application.

This dataset formed the basis for the development of an **AI-based recommendation system** designed to understand and process queries expressed in natural language, significantly improving the catalogue's accessibility and usability.

In line with EOSC requirements, an advanced search system with granular filtering capabilities has been implemented. Based on Elasticsearch and NLP, the engine will eventually be able to handle large volumes of data and return results with high efficiency and accuracy—a key aspect for those working in multidisciplinary contexts with numerous available services. Currently, the catalogue contents are being populated: it will take some time before the database is optimised and can guarantee full search engine efficiency.

Advanced filtering options are available, enabling users to narrow down results based on criteria such as service type, search scope, geographic location, and availability. In addition to the classic keyword search, the system also supports faceted navigation, allowing services to be explored according to multiple attributes. This mode facilitates the discovery process even for users who are unfamiliar with technical terminology.

The use of *Elasticsearch* allows the system to scale horizontally as the number of users and services increases, maintaining high performance and ensuring stability and reliability over time.